

D2.5. Dialog system integrating components developed in T2.2-4

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Abstract	Deliverable D2.5 details the technical integration and orchestration of the ELOQUENCE dialogue system, transforming individual research components into a unified, production-ready backend. It outlines a multi-tier architecture that connects high-performance computing resources on MareNostrum5 with user-facing pilot applications through standardized APIs and secure orchestration frameworks. The report describes how multilingual natural language understanding (NLU), multimodal speech-to-dialog interfaces, and factual grounding mechanisms are combined, all managed by an explainable orchestration layer. Key to this integration is a continuous alignment pipeline, using human feedback and Direct Preference Optimization to maintain safety and factual accuracy, and a federated training paradigm that demonstrates the possibility to protect data privacy.		

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CLI	Command Line Interface
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graphs
DPO	Direct Preference Optimization
DST	Dialogue State Tracking
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FIFO	First-In, First-Out
FIR	Factual Information Retrieval
FL	Federated Learning
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IP	Interactive Playground
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSONL	JSON Lines
KL	Kullback-Leibler
LDES	Local Dynamic Early Stopping
LLM	Large Language Model
LoRA	Low-Rank Adaptation
LVS	Local Vector Store
MEUSLI	Multilingual EU Speech Linear projector
MN5	Mare Nostrum 5
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
OOD	Out-Of-Domain
OOM	Out Of Memory
PCM	Pulse-Code Modulation
QA	Question-Answering
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
REST	Representational State Transfer
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
RMS	Root Mean Square
SFT	Supervised Fine-Tuning
SSH	Secure Shell
TSV	Tab-Separated Values
TTS	Text-to-Speech
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VRAM	Video Random Access Memory
WAV	Waveform Audio File Format
WuW	Wake-Up-Word

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the technical synthesis of research activities conducted within WP2. Functioning as the central technical nexus of the entire ELOQUENCE architecture, this deliverable reports on the transition from isolated modules to a fully orchestrated, production-grade computational backend. The primary objective is to realize a unified dialogue system that consolidates the advancements in natural language understanding from T2.2 (Factual Information Retrieval), T2.3 (Dialog Management), and T2.4 (Alignment through Human Feedback). This integration effort is architecturally significant as it fulfils the project's core mission to deliver context-aware, bias-controlled, and multilingual dialogue systems designed for safety-critical applications.

Specifically, D2.5 serves as the primary vehicle for showcasing the following Key Results (KRs):

- **KR1 (Multilinguality):** Support for all official languages of the 27 EU member states through the integration and development of multilingual LLMs.
- **KR2 (Multimodality):** Development of advanced LLMs that combine latent spaces for both text and speech modalities.
- **KR3 (Adaptation of LLMs):** Support for rapid model adaptation through parameter-efficient techniques and federated learning.
- **KR5 (Contextualization/Grounding):** Grounding LLM outputs in real-world applications to ensure factual reliability.
- **KR9 (Dynamic Constraints):** Mitigation of hallucinations through task-specific constraints, particularly for smart home and call centre environments.

By integrating and orchestrating the outputs from WPs 2, 3, and 4 into a cohesive infrastructure deployed on MareNostrum 5 HPC cluster, the project ensures that its foundational NLU capabilities are ready to serve the user-facing pilot applications developed under WP5. The report details the shift from static model deployment to a dynamic, feedback-driven lifecycle where preference data is ingested into a centralized training pipeline, fulfilling the requirements for Milestone M2.2 and the broader technical objectives of the integration task.

The technical realization of these KRs is evidenced by the system's ability to handle complex, multimodal, and multilingual inputs within a high-performance environment. To address KR1 (Multilinguality) and KR2 (Multimodality), D2.5 integrates sophisticated speech-to-dialog interfaces and multimodal LLMs that support a wide array of European languages across both text and speech modalities. This is achieved through the incorporation of the WP4 speech stack (including well known speech processor like as **Whisper**, **WhisperX**, **Qwen2-Audio** up to the most advanced LLM-based speech recognisers like as **MEUSLI**) as standardized API inputs for the Dialog Manager. Furthermore, the deliverable encapsulates the hierarchical integration of fine-tuned conversational LLMs, addressing KR3 (Adaptation of LLMs) by enabling rapid, domain-specific adaptation via LoRA adapters. This modularity allows the system to easily pivot between the distinct linguistic and procedural domains, ranging from medical emergency services and university guidance scenarios to home environment, without sacrificing performance. Grounding these interactions in verifiable reality is central to KR5 (Contextualization/Grounding), which is fulfilled by integrating the Factual Information Retrieval mechanisms developed in task T2.2, like as classical Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) up to more advanced systems, e.g., capable to grounding responses directly in the speech embedding space. Ensuring system's interactions are rooted in factual accuracy allow that the LLM's outputs are strictly constrained, e.g. by enterprise-specific documentation, thereby mitigating the risk of factual errors in high-stakes environments. Moreover, the system architecture prioritizes the mitigation of LLM hallucinations through the application of dynamic constraints, directly addressing KR9. By utilizing dialogue goal tracking and robust out-of-domain detection logic developed in T2.3, the system can identify when a user's query falls outside its specialized knowledge base, triggering appropriate safety-first fallback responses rather than generating plausible but incorrect information. This safeguard is critical for safety-critical virtual agents where precision is paramount.

Ultimately, to further adapting the ELOQUENCE architecture system described in this deliverable, we rely on an automatic pipeline for continuous alignment. This procedure ensures we can leverage human feedback to iteratively improve core-backend LLMs and incorporating expert feedback from WP6.

Finally, this report confirms the successful achievement of Milestone M2.2 (M21), signalling that the FIR-grounded response generator is fully operational and integrated. This achievement marks the transition of the ELOQUENCE core NLU stack into a state of readiness for real-world deployment across the project's diverse pilot scenarios.

2 Introduction

As the project enters its third year, the focus has shifted from the development of foundational modules to their systematic integration into a cohesive, production-grade dialogue framework. The deliverable D2.5 provides the necessary context for this shift, outlining how the work performed in WP2 contributes to the broader project goals. D2.5 serves as the architectural glue that binds the research outputs of WP2, WP3, and WP4 into a unified backend, which is subsequently exposed to the pilot environments in WP5. This integration is a methodological necessity for achieving the project's KRs regarding bias mitigation, context-awareness, and multilingualism. D2.5 is built upon the prerequisite foundation established in Milestone 2.1 (M12), which defined the baseline LLMs fine-tuned methodology and models for conversational data (D2.1), advancing into a complete grounded response system (Milestone 2.2 – M21), and paving the way towards dialogue models incorporating contextual information (Milestone 3.2 – M28).

To provide a comprehensive view of this integration, this report adopts a differentiated descriptive approach based on the lifecycle of each component. Readers should note that components previously detailed in earlier project deliverables (such as the Federated Training framework in D2.3 or the Speech stack in WP4) are presented here primarily through the lens of their systemic integration and API interoperability. Conversely, modules reaching technical maturity or specific functional configurations within this task (most notably the Dialog Manager) are described with higher granularity to document their internal logic and operational readiness for the upcoming pilots.

A defining feature of the ELOQUENCE architecture is its extensive cross-Work Package dependency network, which D2.5 orchestrates with technical precision. The relationship between WP2 (NLU Integration) and WP4 (Speech & Multilinguality) is particularly vital; D2.5 integrates WP4 speech-to-text components such as fine-tuned **Whisper**, **WhisperX** modules, and the **MEUSLI** framework as standardized API inputs. This allows the WP2 Dialog Manager to process spoken inputs while relying on WP4's language-free semantic representations for effective application domain adaptation. Similarly, the integration between WP2 and WP3 (Explainability) is realized through the incorporation of the **SDialog** Endpoint framework. Developed in WP3, this framework acts as the sophisticated orchestration layer governing agent behaviour, reasoning logic, and rule-based reactions. By embedding these reasoning protocols, as an intermediate orchestration layer, the final output is forwarded to the user interface, ensuring that every response is the result of a controlled, verifiable and explainable decision-making process. This synergy directly supports the project's commitment to transparency and grounded interaction, ensuring that the dialogue policies developed in WP2 are governed by the explainability constraints of WP3.

In the following we outline the contents of the deliverable and the role of each chapter:

- **Chapter 3** details the *system architecture and orchestration framework* that enables the deployment and coordination of all NLU components developed in WP2. It explains how responsibilities are distributed across the Gateway and Compute layers, how inference is orchestrated on MareNostrum 5 via **magma**, and how the system handles secure connectivity and tunnelling constraints inherent to HPC environments.
- **Chapter 4** describes the *API design and interoperability standards* that allow heterogeneous modules (speech encoders, LLMs, retrievers, and feedback processor) to communicate through unified interfaces. This chapter specifies containerisation practices, OpenAI-compatible specification requirements, and standardized I/O conventions needed to ensure scalability, reproducibility, and modular integration.
- **Chapter 5** presents the *UX integration layer*, focusing on the Interactive Playground (IP) and its task-based architecture. This chapter explains how the IP incorporates multimodal interaction, model selection, evaluation workflows, and feedback capture, and how it exposes the system's capabilities to researchers, pilot partners, and automated testing pipelines.
- **Chapter 6** develops the *integration of core NLU components* produced in T2.2–T2.4, including the Dialogue Manager, Dialogue State Tracking (DST) module, SDialog orchestration interface, speech-to-dialog pipelines, RAG-based grounding mechanisms, and text-to-speech (TTS) output. This

chapter describes how these components interact during end-to-end execution and how they jointly contribute to safety-aligned and context-aware behavior.

- **Chapter 7** focuses on the *implementation of user feedback mechanisms* within the integrated system. It explains how feedback queries, behavioral signals, and LLM-based evaluators are incorporated into the live pipeline, enabling real-time behavioral adjustments and the accumulation of high-fidelity preference data.
- **Chapter 8** documents the integration of federated training and its integration into the system's lifecycle. The chapter explains how multilingual clients train local adapters, how updates are aggregated, and how training is orchestrated within distributed HPC environments.
- **Chapter 9** presents the *continuous alignment pipeline*, where human feedback (whether collected via the IP or external annotators) is transformed into preference datasets and used to update the system through Direct Preference Optimization (DPO). This chapter also explains how the pipeline integrates with WP6 ethics requirements and WP1 assessment metrics.
- **Chapter 10** concludes the deliverable by summarizing the achieved integration milestones, discussing remaining challenges, and outlining next steps in preparation for pilot deployment.

Through these chapters, deliverable D2.5 demonstrates how ELOQUENCE evolved from a set of independent research modules into a fully operational, multi-component dialogue system capable of real-world deployment in safety-critical and multilingual scenarios. The integrated system consolidates speech processing, factual grounding, retrieval-augmented generation, explainability, and human-feedback alignment into a coherent architecture that constitutes the technical foundation for the project's pilots under WP5.

The deployment and validation of the system are further intertwined with WP5 (Piloting), WP1 (Assessment), and WP6 (Ethics). The integrated backend is deployed via an SSH tunnelling layer to the project's Gateway Layer, which hosts the WP5 Interactive Playground (IP), as defined in deliverable D5.2. Within this ecosystem, it is critical to distinguish between three operational modalities:

- **Integrated in the IP:** Components like the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) infrastructure and local vector stores are natively embedded within the Playground to provide a unified research environment but also accessible as endpoints to allow flexible communication with external modules, e.g., in the form of LLM tools.
- **Result of Integrated Components:** The complex end-to-end workflows, such as the Spanish Dialogue-Grounded Question-Answering system or the dialogue orchestration, emerge from the successful interoperation of multiple back-end modules (LLM backends, Dialogue Manager, Speech Recogniser, SDialog).
- **Standalone Services:** Certain modules, such as OpenWebUI front-end or Wake-Up-Word detection module, operate as independent services that communicate with the central stack via standardised endpoints.

The establishment of the necessary user multimodal interfaces and infrastructure to consume the D2.5 backend end-points further enrich the Milestone 5.1. Both the Interactive Playground and the Open WebUI user interfaces allow for real-world pilot testing across ELOQUENCE's use case scenarios, where user feedback can be collected and iteratively employed to refine the technologies developed across WP2, WP3, and WP4.

To guarantee the safety and reliability of the integrated system, WP1 has created a set of metrics (see deliverable D1.2) and will use a detailed evaluation framework (that will be reported in upcoming deliverable D1.3) to continuously assess its performance. WP6 is also regularly reviewing the system's technologies to make sure they align with European Union values, protect privacy, and minimize bias. This combined effort ensures the "unified dialogue system" not only achieves its technical goals (Milestones M12 and M21) but is also developed ethically and with consideration for social responsibility.

3 System Architecture and Orchestration Framework

3.1 Infrastructure Distribution and Responsibilities

The system is architected as a multi-tier framework where operational mandates are distributed between a public-facing Gateway Layer and an internal Compute Layer situated on MareNostrum 5 cluster.

Figure 3.1 Multi-tier system architecture between the different hosts involved

The Gateway Layer operates as the centralized orchestrator and external security perimeter of the ecosystem. Its primary mandate involves hosting the user-facing dialogue stack, including the **Interactive Playground**, **Open WebUI**, alongside necessary pilot-specific and task-specific services. Beyond application hosting, Gateway manages the critical networking stack, which is required to access the compute nodes. This is achieved through the establishment of SSH Unix tunnels and reverse port-forwarding. Furthermore, the layer manages all incoming traffic via a **NGINX** reverse proxy.

The Compute Layer, residing on the MN5 environment, provides the resources required for both inference and model training. This layer is responsible for the execution of LLM inference endpoints, typically utilizing optimized engines such as **vLLM**¹ for standard architectures or custom **FastAPI**² implementations within **Singularity**³ containers for multimodal pipelines. In addition to inference, this layer facilitates distributed training and scaling processes, most notably the DPO training cycle we are going to discuss on Section 9.1.

¹ <https://github.com/vllm-project/vllm>

² <https://github.com/fastapi/fastapi>

³ <https://github.com/sylabs/singularity>

3.2 Inference Orchestration via Magma

The orchestration of HPC resources is facilitated by the **magma**⁴ framework. This engine serves as the primary abstraction layer between application logic and **SLURM scheduler**⁵, enabling template-driven workflows. Key capabilities include:

- **Modular Addon Injection:** magma utilizes a flexible system for dynamically loading auxiliary services through specialized shell-based directives. This mechanism allows for the on-demand injection of specialized runtimes (e.g., vLLM, Singularity) into a generic compute job based on the target task requirements.
- **HPC Environment Mapping:** magma ensures that the underlying cluster hardware, including GPU drivers and networking stacks, is correctly mapped inside Singularity containers.

While open-source orchestration alternatives such as **Nextflow**, **Snakemake**, and **Flux** provide robust workflow management, their deployment in HPC environments often necessitates non-trivial integration efforts to bridge the gap between application-level logic and low-level cluster schedulers. Specifically, configuring these tools for the unique hardware topologies and security constraints of a supercomputer like MN5 requires significant administrative overhead to ensure proper functionality and efficient resource allocation.

In contrast, magma offers a specialized, pre-integrated solution that operates transparently on MN5, directly abstracting the SLURM interface through a template-driven engine designed for large-scale AI workloads. By utilizing modular addon injection and automated environment mapping, magma eliminates the need for manual script generation and complex networking workarounds (e.g., SSH tunnelling for services), providing an "out-of-the-box" production-grade backend.

3.3 SSH Endpoint Tunnelling

To facilitate the consumption of inference services by the IP and pilot interfaces, a SSH tunnelling layer is implemented on the project's Gateway host. This connectivity is essential because jobs running inside compute nodes on MN5 are managed as transient, high-density resources that are summoned on demand to ensure optimal hardware utilization. Consequently, inference endpoints are scarce and typically inactive by default, requiring an orchestration logic that accounts for the ephemeral nature of these workloads.

A significant integration challenge is the temporal decoupling between service requests and connectivity establishment. Because MN5 public login nodes lack outbound internet connectivity, it is impossible to initiate SSH sessions from the cluster toward the project infrastructure; all communication must be established as a pull mechanism from the Gateway. Furthermore, supercomputer security policies prevent the simultaneous initiation of secure tunnels at the exact moment a compute job is submitted. To resolve this, the project utilizes a "smart" reconciliation implementation that bridges the gap between the initial resource request and the availability of the remote service. The management of these connections is governed by a hardened orchestration system that automates the mapping of job-scoped remote availability to stable listeners through the following architectural mechanisms:

- **Persistent Connection Management:** The orchestrator maintains stable communication channels to eliminate the overhead of repeated authentication cycles. This strategy minimizes connectivity churn and

⁴ <https://github.com/langtech-bsc/magma>

⁵ Slurm (<https://github.com/schedmd/slurm>) is an open-source workload manager and job scheduler for Linux clusters. It is widely used in HPC environments like supercomputers to allocate compute nodes, manage job queues, and optimize resource usage across many users.

prevents triggering security-based rate-limiting mechanisms on the access infrastructure during high-frequency request cycles.

- **Reactive Connection Supervision:** Communication links are continuously monitored by a specialized supervision daemon that ensures automatic recovery during network fluctuations. This system handles the transition period while backend jobs are in a pending state, automatically activating transport once the remote service reports readiness.

This connectivity strategy ensures that modules remain securely isolated within high-density compute partitions while remaining accessible as standardized endpoints for validation and evaluation.

Beyond the technical validation within the ELOQUENCE research infrastructure, the transition of this framework into a commercial-grade product requires a shift from research-oriented "pull" mechanisms to a scalable, service-oriented architecture. From a business perspective, the current reliance on transient HPC compute nodes and manual tunnel reconciliation represents a significant barrier to the "high availability" standards expected in safety-critical sectors like emergency services or healthcare. **To reach market readiness, the system would necessitate the implementation of a permanent, auto-scaling inference cluster** (e.g., using Kubernetes or managed GPU instances) that eliminates the need for ephemeral SSH tunnels.

4 API Design and Interoperability Standards

4.1 Component Containerisation

To ensure deterministic reproducibility across development and production environments of the project, we instrumentalized a framework for systematic containerisation lifecycle. Starting from a **Docker** file template, developers refine it based on their requirements; we encourage selecting foundational images that provide pre-compiled CUDA kernels optimized for the NVIDIA GPUs present at MN5.

To accelerate the iterative development cycle, a Docker Compose strategy is implemented locally. This setup leverages asynchronous server "hot-reload" mechanisms through bind mounts, permitting researchers to modify custom inference logic in real-time within a containerised environment that accurately mirrors the production stack before any codebase is promoted to the supercomputer.

A critical validation phase within this local workflow involves network isolation testing. We encourage developers to verify their implementations using the `network.default.internal: true` directive in their Compose configurations. This configuration restricts outbound traffic, effectively simulating the environment of MN5 compute nodes. By successfully running model inference in this isolated mode, developers ensure that all requisite assets are fully encapsulated within the Docker image prior to conversion into a **Singularity** artifact.

This conversion into Singularity artifact is necessary as Docker daemons introduce privilege escalation vulnerabilities. Additionally, Singularity containers are more scalable by nature, thus profiting from performance gains when running on HPC environment. Consequently, we operate an automated Docker-to-Singularity CI/CD pipeline using an internal tool developed by BSC.

4.2 Standardised Input/Output

Interoperability between different modules is achieved by strictly enforcing the JSON-based OpenAI API Reference⁶. This structural imperative ensures that all integrated components present a uniform interface, preventing the proliferation of non-standard endpoints that would complicate system-wide integration.

⁶ <https://developers.openai.com/api/reference/resources/chat>

- **Textual Interoperability** ([/v1/chat/completions](#)): All chat-based modules must implement this specification, allowing the frontend to seamlessly interchange backend adapters or base models without modification to the integration logic.
- **Speech Interoperability** ([/v1/audio/transcriptions](#)): Audio processing modules utilize this to ingest multipart audio payloads, returning structured JSON containing transcribed segments, precise word-level timestamps, and speaker diarisation metadata.

4.3 Service Exposure and Design Patterns

We utilize **FastAPI** for wrapping and exposing the logic thus allowing the interaction between models and custom pipelines and other components of the Interactive Playground. A critical design constraint enforced for system stability is Module-Level Initialization. In the context of HPC, heavy computational assets, such as models, must be loaded into GPU VRAM exclusively during the initial module import phase.

Instantiating model constructors within localized request-handling functions (e.g., inside a **POST** route) is strictly interdicted. Such dynamic allocation during active request handling precipitates severe GPU Memory Exhaustion OOM crashes, and prohibitive response latency due to redundant loading sequences. By enforcing global model initialization, the framework guarantees that a single, persistent model instance resides in memory, ensuring inference readiness and maintaining a stable response profile.

5 UX integration

5.1 Interactive Playground

The Interactive Playground, IP (detailed in deliverable [D5.2](#)), constitutes one of the contributions of the ELOQUENCE project infrastructure, designed and implemented as a unified environment in which throughout an UI the diverse AI capabilities developed across the project's work packages can be accessed, evaluated, and demonstrated in an integrated manner. The rationale for its development stems from the practical impossibility of accommodating the project's specific and heterogeneous component roster (spanning multiple language model families, speech processing pipelines, and a custom retrieval infrastructure) within any generic commercial interface. The platform was therefore built from the ground up as a project-specific research and validation environment, serving simultaneously as a demonstration tool, a structured evaluation framework, and a composable service component accessible to all consortium members.

As illustrated in Figure 3.1, the IP occupies a central architectural position within the broader ELOQUENCE system, sitting behind a proxy and exposed port layer through which user interactions arrive, and connecting outward to language model instances, speech processing services, or the retrieval infrastructure. The platform is architecturally grounded in two complementary frameworks: **Gradio**⁷, which provides the web-based graphical interface, and **FastAPI**, which exposes the same underlying functionality through a structured REST API. Both interfaces share an identical backend, ensuring full consistency between what a human user achieves through the graphical interface and what an external system achieves programmatically. This dual-interface design reflects a deliberate architectural decision to support two distinct usage modalities: interactive use by researchers, consortium members, and external reviewers; and programmatic use by automated workflows including batch evaluation pipelines, integration testing routines, and downstream system components that consume the platform's capabilities as a service.

⁷ <https://github.com/gradio-app/gradio>

Operationally, the Interactive Playground is designed to run as a single Compose service on a virtualized Linux environment. For stable development and consistent document ingestion, the deployed configuration consists of 4 vCPUs and 12 to 16 GiB of RAM. The system utilizes a CPU-only PyTorch installation for its default embedding fallbacks (e.g., MiniLM) and handles ingestion in batches of 128, which can result in transient spikes in resource utilization. To ensure high availability and prevent storage-related failures during model downloads or index growth, a disk budget of 25 to 40 GiB for Docker storage and 10 to 20 GiB for the project bind-mount filesystem is recommended; notably, **heavy ingestion of larger corpora may necessitate a total free disk budget exceeding 50 GiB and higher vCPUs resources.**

The application is containerised using **Docker**⁸ and deployed as a single self-contained service, with all persistent data — vector indexes, user workspaces, configuration files, conversation histories, system prompts, and feedback records — stored in a mounted volume that survives container restarts and updates. The platform implements a custom middleware layer that interprets forwarded path prefix headers, specifically `x-forwarded-prefix` and `x-script-name`, and strips subpath prefixes before internal routing, enabling deployment at configurable subpaths within shared server environments without modification to application code. User authentication is managed through a **SQLite**⁹ database, with each authenticated user assigned a private workspace on the filesystem serving as the persistent store for their saved system prompts, conversation histories, and custom retriever configurations. Beyond the system-level retriever configuration, individual users may additionally register private retriever instances hosted on their own local network, which are stored within their private workspace and take precedence over the system-level default when present, enabling more secure handling of sensitive documentary collections without routing data through shared infrastructure. A shared feedback store collects evaluation data contributed by all users, forming a growing corpus of annotated interactions available for analysis and export. The platform's interaction model is organised around a set of discrete task configurations, each tailored to a specific AI capability and serving as the primary unit through which users and external systems engage with the platform's functionality.

5.1.1 Task Configuration System

A defining architectural characteristic of the Interactive Playground is its task-driven interaction model. Rather than offering a monolithic chat interface, the platform organises all interactions around discrete task configurations, each defined declaratively through a JSON file specifying four core fields: the task name, the required interface type (text or audio), whether retrieval-augmented generation should be activated, and the service routing strategy to be applied (local or remote). Audio-oriented tasks carry an additional `audio_mode` field that further specialises their runtime behaviour. This declarative approach confers meaningful extensibility: introducing a new task type that follows an existing interaction pattern requires only the addition of a new configuration file, with no modifications to the task dispatch logic in `task_handlers.py`, which is genuinely data-driven and reads all branching conditions directly from the config. Tasks that require custom UI visibility behaviour — such as conditional display of RAG controls or summarization triggers — do additionally require localised changes to the interface layer in `app_handlers.py`, a bounded and well-isolated modification. The task system thereby acts as a stable abstraction layer separating the definition of what a task is from the mechanics of how it is executed.

From a business perspective, this architecture directly supports the iterative, pilot-driven development model of the project. New interaction paradigms (such as domain-specific retrieval tasks, specialised audio workflows, or externally routed enterprise integrations via the remote service mode) can be introduced and evaluated with minimal development overhead, reducing the cost of experimentation and accelerating the feedback cycle

⁸ <https://www.docker.com>

⁹ <https://sqlite.org/index.html>

between technical implementation and end-user validation. The clean separation between task definition and execution logic also means that task configurations can be maintained and extended by personnel with limited software development expertise, lowering the barrier to platform customisation across deployment contexts.

Five task configurations are active at the current development stage:

- **Basic LLM:** provides a direct conversational interface to any of the available text-based language models without retrieval augmentation, suited to general-purpose dialogue, prompt experimentation, and the establishment of response baselines.
- **RAG:** enables retrieval-augmented question answering by connecting the language model to the platform's local vector store. User queries are used to retrieve semantically relevant document chunks from a pre-built index, which are assembled into a structured context and injected into the model prompt via a **Jinja2** template that includes explicit grounding instructions, directing the model to base its responses exclusively on the provided documents and to acknowledge when the answer cannot be found in the retrieved context. This configuration is described in greater technical detail in Section 6.3.1.
- **Summarization:** applies the language model to the task of condensing a completed multi-turn conversation into a concise summary, serialising the full conversation history into a structured text representation and submitting it through the same request pipeline used by all other task types.
- **Audio QA:** supports spoken-language question answering through two runtime-selectable sub-modes. In the Whisper + LLM sub-mode, spoken input is first transcribed by a Whisper-class automatic speech recognition model, after which the transcription is passed to a text-based language model for response generation. In the Speech LLM sub-mode, an end-to-end speech-capable model processes the raw audio directly without an intermediate transcription step.
- **Transcription:** provides standalone speech-to-text functionality, routing audio input exclusively to Whisper-class models and returning the transcribed text without further language model processing.

5.1.2 Language Model Integration

The execution of each task configuration relies on the language models available to the platform, which span both text and audio modalities and are accessed through a unified interface abstraction that decouples the platform from any specific serving infrastructure. The platform integrates a curated set of language models spanning text and audio modalities, all accessed through an OpenAI-compatible API interface that standardises the request and response format across diverse model backends. This interface abstraction allows the platform to connect to models served by any compatible inference framework (including **vLLM**, **TGI**¹⁰, **llama.cpp**¹¹ or **Ollama**¹²) without changes to client-side code, decoupling the platform from any specific serving infrastructure. The models currently deployed include **Salamandra**, a seven-billion-parameter instruction-tuned model; **Gemma**, a twenty-seven-billion-parameter instruction-tuned model; **Qwen2.5-Audio**, an end-to-end speech-capable language model; **Whisper**, a large-vocabulary automatic speech recognition model based on the **large-v3-turbo** architecture; and **SDialog**¹³ serving task-specific conversational workflows.

Despite sharing a common API interface, different language model families require meaningfully different prompt construction strategies, as the expected message format (specifically how system instructions, contextual

¹⁰ <https://github.com/huggingface/text-generation-inference>

¹¹ <https://github.com/ggerganov/llama.cpp>

¹² <https://github.com/ollama/ollama>

¹³ SDialog provides middleware communication between UI and LLM backends, exposing OpenAI-compatible endpoints. Unlike a language model, it acts purely as an-interface layer that “taps” or proxies interactions without performing inference itself, but from the point of view of a user (IP) it connects as a standard LLM’s endpoint, see Section 6.1.3.1.

information, and conversation history should be structured within the message list) varies substantially across architectures. The platform addresses this through a hierarchy of model-specific interactor classes, each implementing the appropriate message construction logic for its target model family. Salamandra expects a dedicated system role message carrying both the system prompt and any retrieved context. Gemma does not support a system role in its chat template and requires the system prompt to be prepended to the first user turn. Qwen2.5-Audio constructs messages in which audio content is transmitted as a base64-encoded WAV payload within a structured content array, with no text component in the final user turn when audio is present. Whisper is accessed through the audio transcriptions endpoint rather than the chat completions endpoint and returns plain text rather than a structured message. This model-specific formatting layer ensures that each model receives inputs in the exact structure its architecture expects, preventing prompt construction errors that would otherwise silently degrade response quality.

A context window management mechanism operates across all text-based model interactions. Before a request is dispatched, the platform computes the approximate token count of the fully assembled message (including system prompt, retrieved context, and conversation history) using **tiktoken** for GPT-family models and a word-count approximation for other architectures, and compares this against the known context length of the target model. If the assembled message exceeds the available window, the platform applies a greedy document-dropping strategy, removing the least-ranked retrieved document and recomputing the token count iteratively until the message fits within the model's constraints, always preserving a safety buffer of 512 tokens to accommodate the generated response. This mechanism ensures that context overflow errors never propagate to the model endpoint and that the maximum amount of relevant retrieved context is always preserved within the available window.

5.1.3 Audio Pipeline

The platform includes a complete browser-to-model audio processing pipeline implemented without reliance on external audio APIs. Audio capture is handled within the browser through the Web **MediaRecorder** API, which records in WebM format by default. The recorded audio is transmitted to the server in one of two modes: either as a complete recording via the [POST /stream_finalize](#) endpoint, which is the mode used by the graphical interface, or as a sequence of 250-millisecond chunks streamed periodically during capture via the [POST /stream](#) endpoint, which is available through the REST API for real-time processing. Upon reception, the audio enters a server-side processing pipeline that first identifies the format through magic byte inspection of the binary header — supporting WAV, OGG, FLAC, MP3, MP4, WebM, and AVI formats — and then converts the audio to WAV format using **pydub**¹⁴ and **ffmpeg**¹⁵ where necessary, as both Whisper and the platform's audio encoding utilities operate on WAV input. For ASR-based pipelines, the resulting WAV bytes are passed directly to the Whisper transcription endpoint; for end-to-end audio model pipelines, the audio is base64-encoded and embedded as a structured payload within the chat message. A language selection parameter propagates through the entire pipeline, enabling the ASR component to be directed toward a specific target language, which is of relevance given ELOQUENCE's multilingual scope and the diversity of languages represented across the project's pilot scenarios.

5.1.4 Evaluation and Feedback Framework

The Interactive Playground incorporates a structured human-in-the-loop evaluation framework designed to capture rich annotation data during normal research usage. After each model response, users may provide binary feedback through a thumbs-up or thumbs-down interaction, optionally supplemented by free-text commentary through an additional feedback field. Each submission captures a self-contained interaction record comprising the

¹⁴ <https://github.com/jiaaro/pydub>

¹⁵ <https://git.ffmpeg.org/ffmpeg.git>

timestamp, the contributing user identity, a boolean helpfulness indicator, any free-text commentary provided, the active model name, the system prompt in effect at the time of the interaction, the text excerpts retrieved from the vector store when the interaction involved document retrieval, the final generated response, and the complete conversation history. This structured schema ensures that feedback records are fully reproducible and self-contained, supporting downstream analysis without requiring reconstruction of the original interaction context.

Collected feedback is surfaced through a dedicated tab in the platform interface providing column-based filtering and a direct download facility and is equally accessible programmatically through the `GET /feedback` endpoint, which accepts filter column and filter value query parameters enabling server-side subsetting without downloading the full dataset. Complementing the interactive feedback mechanism, the `POST /batch_query` endpoint accepts a JSON file containing multiple multi-turn conversations and processes each turn sequentially, maintaining conversation history across turns and returning the fully processed conversation set. This facility supports systematic evaluation workflows in which pre-defined test dialogue sets are run through the system and outputs collected for offline analysis without requiring manual interaction through the UI.

5.2 Open WebUI

Open WebUI¹⁶ is a user interface that enables real-time interaction between humans and LLMs. This interface serves as a platform where users can type their input and receive responses from LLMs. In this project, Open WebUI plays a critical role by acting as the front-end interface that allows users to interact with the LLM and provide valuable feedback on its responses. A decisive factor in selecting this platform was its support for different feedback mechanisms which were already implemented, significantly accelerating the integration of the alignment loop.

Besides the primary purpose of Open WebUI for making the interaction with LLMs more accessible and engaging, it also showcases the easy plug and play for shifting components (as the UI) within the IP. Open WebUI also facilitates the collection of feedback, which is vital for model refinement and improvement. It allows users to provide feedback on various aspects of the model's performance, including the quality of answers, their helpfulness, and their relevance.

Key features of Open WebUI include:

- **Real-time Interaction:** Users can type questions and immediately receive answers from the model.
- **Feedback Collection:** The interface enables users to express dissatisfaction or provide constructive feedback on the model's responses.
- **User-Friendly:** Open WebUI is designed to be simple to use, even for non-technical users, ensuring that feedback can be collected from a broad audience.
- **Open WebUI's implements "Model Arena"** or evaluation mode pits multiple LLMs side-by-side against the same prompt. Users get responses from each model simultaneously and provide pairwise feedback (thumbs up/down) to rank preferences. This creates a personal/team leaderboard tracking win rates across models based on your votes. Sibling responses (same prompt, different models) enable direct A/B comparisons for systematic feedback collection. Figure 5.1.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/open-webui/open-webui>

Figure 5.1 Showcase of “Model Arena” functionality within Open WebUI interface

Open WebUI serves as the primary interface for collecting high-fidelity preference signals as stated on [deliverable D2.4](#). The platform was selected for its capabilities in capturing feedback across multiple dimensions and provision of raw input data for DPO alignment loop.

The environment is instantiated using a Docker Compose stack focused on live development. By setting bind mounts, changes on the app are reflected immediately. Additionally, application logic is decoupled from persistent storage to ensure that collected datasets and user configurations remain intact across lifecycles.

6 Integration of Core NLU Components

The ELOQUENCE dialogue system's technical realization relies on a modular, multi-tier architecture that orchestrates specialized Natural Language Understanding (NLU) and speech processing modules into a unified backend. As illustrated in Figure 6.1, the system is distributed across a public-facing Gateway Layer (hosting the user environment and proxy interfaces) and a high-performance Compute Layer at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC).

The orchestration framework manages the following critical data flows and component interactions:

- **User Interface & Access:** End-users interact via Open WebUI, the Interactive Playground’s User Interface, or mobile-based Wake-Up-Word (WuW) detection, all routed through a secure proxy layer.
- **Central Orchestration:** The IP and SDialog framework act as the central logic hubs, coordinating requests between the conversational agents and specialized backend services.
- **Compute Cluster Services:** Heavy computational tasks are offloaded to the GPU cluster, which hosts:
 - **LLM Instances:** Foundation models for text generation and reasoning.
 - **NER Instances:** Named Entity Recognition services used by the Dialog Manager to track clinical and task-specific slot values.
 - **Speech Stack:** A comprehensive suite of audio processors, including Whisper/X, MEUSLI for end-to-end speech-to-text, and Factual Information Retrieval (FIR) for grounded responses.

- Knowledge Grounding:** The Retriever module interfaces with a local Vector Store (LanceDB¹⁷) to provide real-time, domain-specific context, ensuring model outputs are anchored in verifiable documentation.

The following subsections detail the internal logic, API specifications, and integration patterns for each of these core components.

Figure 6.1 Showcase of all modules present and their interactions with other modules.

6.1 Dialog orchestration

The Dialog Orchestration section presents the core dialog orchestration components that enable structured, adaptive, and reproducible conversational workflows within the system. The three modules that manage how user interactions are interpreted, tracked, and acted upon are presented here. First, the Dialog Manager defines an entity-driven dialog policy, dynamically guiding the conversation by generating targeted questions based on the evolving sequence of extracted entities related to a user’s health concern and the dialog history. Complementing this, the Dialogue State Tracking (DST) module leverages a speech-enabled LLM backbone to process user input at each turn, producing a rich representation that includes the audio transcript, identified domain, and extracted slot values. Finally, SDialog introduces an orchestration layer with different abstractions that enable reproducible conversational workflows and structured representations of multi-turn dialogues.

6.1.1 Dialog Manager

The implemented dialog manager is adapted as a task-oriented dialog system, e.g. designed to support paediatric medical call centre workflows by systematically collecting clinically relevant information from the caller, like as in the intended implementation of the Pilot 4. Its primary objective is to structure a conversation in a way that ensures a coherent dialog flow and constrained to the use case needs. In the case of Pilot 4, a medical expert should receive a complete and coherent summary of the child’s health condition as described by the child’s

¹⁷ LanceDB is an open-source, embedded vector database for multimodal AI applications. <https://github.com/lancedb/lancedb>

parent during a call centre interaction. Pilot 4 strictly prohibits any medical advice from the system, while Pilot 2 directs it to self-regulate and minimize bias in academic career recommendations. This dual setup tests safety constraints alongside fairness controls in LLM deployments.

In the medical domain use case, it operates through a controlled multi-turn dialogue, with a maximum of ten questions asked to the caller from the system side. Its internal state includes the full dialog history, the detected health issue category, and a dynamically updated set of extracted entities. This entity-state driven design allows the dialog manager to remain context-aware and goal-oriented throughout the interaction.

A central feature of the system is its entity-based dialog orchestration. Using a finetuned named entity recognition model, the dialog manager extracts domain-specific entities (e.g., SYMPTOM, DURATION, TEMPERATURE, BEHAVIOR) from user utterances and stores them in a structured format. These entities are mapped against predefined entity-priority lists associated with different complaint categories (such as fever, cough, rash or other). Based on the detected category and the entities already collected, the system identifies which critical information is still missing and needs to be asked. This enables the dialog manager to ask targeted, non-redundant questions that progressively fill information gaps, ensuring that each turn contributes meaningfully toward a comprehensive clinical situation.

The decision-making process for generating the next system response is handled by a large language model acting as a “judge.” This component receives the full dialog history, the accumulated entities, and the list of missing high-priority entity types and determines whether to ask a new question or terminate the conversation. To generate the next system utterance/question to the user, the system strongly considers the entity priority list for the specific health issue and the dialog history until that turn. This results in a coherent and adaptive conversational flow, where each system prompt is grounded both in the historical dialogue and in the structured representation of extracted information.

To ensure robustness and domain compliance, the system incorporates an Out-Of-Domain (OOD) detection module. This component evaluates each user utterance to determine whether it remains within the scope of information gathering. If a user attempts to request medical advice or introduces irrelevant content, the system flags the input as off-topic. In such cases, it responds with a standardized message indicating that it can only collect information for the medical expert and then re-asks the previous question. This mechanism prevents the system from generating inappropriate responses while keeping the conversation aligned with its intended purpose.

Finally, once sufficient information has been gathered or the maximum number of system turns is reached, the dialog manager concludes the interaction and generates a concise summary for the doctor. This summary is produced by the language model using both the full conversation history and the structured entity set, ensuring that all critical details (such as symptoms, duration, severity, and relevant context) are included. The result is a clear, clinically useful narrative that can support downstream medical assessment, effectively bridging the gap between unstructured user input and structured clinical documentation.

In the following subsections, the individual modules and their functionality that constitute the dialog manager are described. The goal is to provide a clear overview of how each component contributes to the overall dialog orchestration process. It should be noted that these modules are still under development and are expected to be improved, particularly in the context of the pilot implementation. Thus, their descriptions presented below reflect their current and not their final operational state.

6.1.1.1 User Issue Category Recognition

The user issue recognition module is responsible for identifying the main child’s health issue described by the parent in their first utterance. The user utterance is sent to an LLM which is prompted to recognize the child’s health issue among a predefined fixed set of possible categories (e.g., fever, cough, rash, etc.) along with clear rules for disambiguation. The model is forced to return exactly one category. If the user utterance does not align to any of the predefined categories, the system classifies the child’s health issue as “other”. This classification step is important because it determines the overall direction of the dialog; it selects the relevant priority entity types

and guides the system in asking the most appropriate follow-up questions to gather clinically useful information for the doctor. Figure 6.2 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the prompt used for this module.

```
( "system", f""You are a medical call center health issue complaint classifier.
Task:
Classify the parent's complaint about the child's health issue into EXACTLY ONE of the following categories:
fever, cough, rash, diarrhea, constipation, injury, feeding, sleep, eye, behavior, development, post_vaccination, cold,
allergy, other
Category definitions:
- fever: elevated body temperature or feeling hot
- cough: dry or wet cough without primary cold symptoms
- rash: skin redness, bumps, itching, or irritation
- diarrhea: frequent loose or watery stools
- constipation: difficulty passing stool or infrequent bowel movements
- injury: physical trauma, fall, wound, burn, swelling from impact
- feeding: eating, breastfeeding, appetite, vomiting after feeding
- sleep: sleep problems, waking frequently, difficulty falling asleep
- eye: eye redness, discharge, swelling, irritation
- behavior: unusual crying, irritability, mood or behavioral changes
- post_vaccination: symptoms clearly occurring after a recent vaccine
- cold: runny nose, congestion, mild cough, typical cold symptoms
- allergy: sneezing, itchy eyes, rash triggered by allergen exposure
- other: use only if none of the above apply
Disambiguation rules:
- If fever happens after vaccination → post_vaccination
- If runny nose + mild cough → cold
- If itching/sneezing triggered by environment → allergy
- If symptom does not clearly match any category → other
Output rules:
- Return ONLY the category name.
- Do not explain
- Do not return multiple categories.
- The output must be lowercase.""",)
("user", "{complaint}")
```

Figure 6.2 The prompt used to instruct the LLM recognise the parent's child health issue.

6.1.1.2 Finetuned NER Model

The Name Entity Recognition model used in the task-oriented dialog manager has been described in [deliverable D3.2](#). The base model is the multilingual version of **GLiNERv2.1**. To finetune it we used the entity labelled UNS multi-turn dialog dataset which is directly related to the Pilot4. The model can perform NER among 30 entity types and its performance both in English and in Serbian has been reported in [deliverable D3.2](#).

6.1.1.3 Entity-Aware System Response

The proposed dialog policy follows an entity-based logic, where system behaviour is guided by a structured entity sequence of relevant to the health issue entity types. Specifically, the policy is derived from the extraction of a priority entity sequence, defined as the most probable ordering of entities that should be asked by the system, conditioned on the health issue identified at the beginning of the dialogue (e.g., from the child's main symptom described by the parent). This sequence reflects the typical triage reasoning process, capturing which information (e.g., **QUANTITY**, **DURATION**, **SYMPTOM**, **BEHAVIOR**, **INTERVENTION**) should be queried and in what order.

To estimate this priority sequence, UNS' corpus of 150 multi-turn, entity-annotated dialogues is leveraged, and statistical sequence modelling techniques are applied. These include methods such as Markov Transition Matrices, which model the probability of transitioning from one entity type to the next, and Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), which capture dominant paths and branching structures in the dialogue flow. The resulting policy provides an interpretable and data-driven mechanism for guiding question selection in a task-oriented medical dialogue system.

6.1.1.4 Out-Of-Domain Detection

The Out-Of-Domain (OOD) detection module ensures that the dialog remains focused on information gathering. Any user utterance that asks anything that the system is not allowed or responsible to answer is considered as OOD and is handled appropriately. After each user utterance is given, it is evaluated by a dedicated classifier implemented using an In-Context Learning LLM. The classifier receives the user's input along with a prompt that clearly defines what constitutes on-topic versus off-topic behaviour and performs binary classification.

If the utterance is identified as off topic (OOD), such as when the user asks for medical advice or introducing irrelevant queries, the system responds with a standardized message explaining that it can only assist in collecting information for the doctor. Instead of updating the dialog state or extracting entities, it re-asks the last system question, guiding the user back to the intended conversational path. At Figure 6.3, is the currently zero-shot prompt used to instruct the LLM to decide whether a user utterance is OOD or not.

```
( "system",  
  ""You are an Out-Of-Domain classifier for a pediatric medical call center service.  
  Given the user's utterance, determine if it is:  
  - on-topic: the user is describing the child's symptoms, history, or answering a question related to the child's health issue.  
  - off-topic: the user is asking for medical advice ("what should I do?", "is it serious?", "should I give medicine?"), or making  
  irrelevant comments (e.g. asking for the weather).  
  If off-topic, output "OFF". If on-topic, output "ON". Return only the word.""", ),  
("user", "{utterance}")
```

Figure 6.3 The zero-shot prompt used to instruct the model perform OOD detection

6.1.1.5 Dialog Summarization

The dialog summarization functionality is executed when the interaction is finished, once either sufficient information has been collected or the maximum number of allowed system turns has been reached. Then the system invokes a summarization instructed LLM, which receives as input both the dialog history and the structured set of accumulated entities. The dialog history is formatted as a sequence of alternating nurse–caller utterances, while the entities are provided in a structured JSON format, ensuring that both unstructured dialog context and structured entity signals are considered. At Figure 6.4, is the currently zero-shot prompt used to instruct the LLM to summarize the dialog.

```
("system",
  """"You are a dialogue summarizer. Given the full conversation between a parent and a nurse, write a concise summary
for the doctor.
Include: main child's health issue, key symptoms, duration, any relevant history, and any other important details.
You are also given the entities referred at the dialogue and you need to include all entities referred into the dialog
summary.
The summary should be in plain English, about 3-5 sentences, and ready to be read by a physician.""", )
("user",
  "Entities:\n{entities}\n\nConversation:\n{history}\n\nDialog Summary:", )
```

Figure 6.4 The zero-shot prompt used to instruct the LLM perform dialog summarization.

6.1.2 Dialogue State Tracking

The Dialogue State Tracking (DST) endpoint exposes the functionality of the DST system described in [deliverable D2.1](#), and subsequently published in (Sedláček, Yusuf, Svec, Hegde, & Kesiraju, 2025). The system consists of a speech-LLM backbone identical to the ones presented in D2.1, utilizing **WavLM-large**¹⁸ as the speech encoder, a 2-layer connector module to map the WavLM output speech representations into the embedding space of the downstream LLM, and the LLM itself, which in this case is **OLMo-1B**¹⁹ in the base/small version of the system, and **Gemma2-9B-Instruct**²⁰ in the larger, more capable version of the system.

The systems were first pretrained for the ASR objective on the **LibriSpeech** (Panayotov, Chen, Povey, & Khudanpur, 2015), **How2** (Sanabria, et al., 2018) and **Fisher** (Cieri, Miller, & Walker, 2004) datasets, and subsequently finetuned for DST using the **SpokenWOZ** (Si, et al., 2023) and **Speech-Aware MultiWOZ** (Soltau, et al., 2023) datasets, achieving SOTA on SpokenWOZ DST. Further training details are provided in the Interspeech publication in (Sedláček, Yusuf, Svec, Hegde, & Kesiraju, 2025).

The input/output formatting for the DST models is a crucial aspect that defines the use case for this system. As with most DST systems, given a transcript of the conversation history between a user and an agent plus the current user turn/request in spoken form, the system predicts the domains and corresponding slots (key-value pairs) in JSON format for the whole conversation up to the current turn. The formatting and the permissible values of slots, the available domains and slot keys are defined by the dataset ontology. Apart from the dialogue state prediction, the model additionally transcribes the current user turn, as it will have to be appended to the conversation history for processing the next conversation turn. An example output of the system is depicted in Figure 6.5.

¹⁸ <https://huggingface.co/microsoft/wavlm-large>

¹⁹ <https://huggingface.co/allenai/OLMo-1B>

²⁰ <https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-2-9b-it>

```
{
  "transcript": "No, I don't think I need email. Thank you.",
  "domains": [
    "profile",
    "restaurant"
  ],
  "slots": {
    "profile": {
      "name": "Kathleen Romaine"
    },
    "restaurant": {
      "day": "Saturday",
      "people": "3",
      "time": "13:10",
      "area": "West",
      "food": "Indian"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 6.5 Example output of the DST system with a state prediction.

6.1.2.1 Implementation and Deployment

The system is exposed as a service via a **FastAPI** application, specifically designed to maintain interoperability with the project's orchestration layer by mimicking the OpenAI Audio API specification. The service exposes a standardized `POST /v1/audio/transcriptions` endpoint that handles multipart form data containing the audio payload and model identifiers.

The inference pipeline is governed by a unified custom class. At service startup, the application performs a global model initialization, loading a consolidated checkpoint that includes the speech encoder, the bridge network, and the LLM weights. To ensure compatibility with the heterogeneous audio formats encountered in pilot scenarios—such as varying sample rates or bit depths in MP3 and WAV files—the API implements a robust pre-processing layer.

The raw model output is processed by a semantic parser designed to handle the stochastic nature of LLM generation. This parser includes specialized error-correction logic to extract the transcript, domains, and slot key-value pairs while stripping common artifacts such as Markdown code fences or malformed JSON strings.

For deployment, the service is containerized using **Singularity** and orchestrated with **magma**. The production image is derived from an optimized **text-generation-inference** plus all necessary dependencies necessary to make the whole pipeline function flawlessly.

6.1.3 SDialog Endpoint

The **SDialog** Endpoint component provides the logical coordination layer that governs how conversational agents behave and interact within the system. The SDialog (Burdisso, et al., 2026) framework introduces standardized abstractions such as **Dialog**, **Turn**, **Persona**, and **Agent**, enabling reproducible multi-agent conversational workflows and structured dialogue representations. Through these abstractions, agents encapsulate an LLM together with persona definitions, contextual information, memory, and optional tools, allowing the system to produce controlled and contextually coherent multi-turn interactions.

Central to this mechanism is the orchestration layer, which dynamically governs agent behaviour during conversation generation. Orchestrators act as lightweight controllers that observe the current dialogue state and inject instructions or constraints into the agent's response generation process. These controllers can operate either transiently or persistently across multiple turns, enabling rule-based reactions, length constraints, probabilistic behavioural changes, or semantic response guidance. Because orchestrators can be composed into

pipelines, they allow complex conversational behaviours to emerge through modular control logic while maintaining clear separation between the underlying language model and dialogue management policies.

To integrate with the broader ELOQUENCE Dialogue system architecture, SDialog agents can be exposed through an OpenAI-compatible REST API endpoint. Using the built-in serving mechanism, an agent instance can be deployed as a network service accessible by external applications such as **Open WebUI** or other API clients. This endpoint allows the Gateway Layer to route incoming user requests to the dialog orchestration service, which then coordinates agent reasoning and response generation before forwarding the final output back to the interface. In this way, the SDialog endpoint functions as the bridge between the user-facing applications hosted on the Gateway Layer and the underlying inference infrastructure of the Compute Layer, enabling controlled, orchestrated dialogue generation at scale.

6.1.3.1 *Serving Agents via REST API.*

SDialog allows you to expose any Agent over an OpenAI/Ollama-compatible REST API using the `serve()` method to talk to it from tools like Open WebUI, Ollama GUI, or simple HTTP clients.

```
from sdialog.agents import Agent

# Let's create an example agent
support = Agent(name="Support")

# And serve it on port 1333 (default host 0.0.0.0)
support.serve(port=1333) # Connect client to base URL localhost:1333
```

For example, to run Open WebUI in **Docker** locally, just set `OLLAMA_BASE_URL` to point to port 1333 in the same machine when launching the container:

```
docker run -d -e OLLAMA_BASE_URL=http://host.docker.internal:1333 \
  -p 3030:8080 \
  -v open-webui:/app/backend/data --name open-webui \
  --restart always ghcr.io/open-webui/open-webui:main
```

Then open `http://localhost:3030` in your browser to chat with the agent.

For serving multiple agents under a single endpoint, use Server's `serve()`, as in the following example:

```
from sdialog.agents import Agent
from sdialog.server import Server

# Create multiple agents
agent1 = Agent(name="AgentOne")
agent2 = Agent(name="AgentTwo")

# Serve both agents on port 1333 (select them by name from the GUI)
Server.serve([agent1, agent2], port=1333)
```

6.2 Speech-to-Dialog interfaces

6.2.1 Whisper-like endpoints

6.2.1.1 Whisper baseline

Whisper service provides an ASR transformer-based foundation model from OpenAI; this module is deployed as a service hosted on MN5. For deploying this service, we use magma framework using the **vLLM** setup. The implementation utilizes a Singularity container based on the **vllm-openai**²¹ Docker image, which has been extended to support both Whisper and WhisperX systems.

As this implementation is backed by vLLM, the service supports and exposes a RESTful interface compliant with the OpenAI [/v1/audio/transcriptions](#) specification, enabling the dialogue orchestrator to treat the ASR module as a standardized component within the larger system architecture.

6.2.1.2 WhisperX baseline

WhisperX²² extends the baseline capabilities of Whisper by providing word-level alignment and speaker diarization, which are required for pilot scenarios. This system is deployed using the shared Singularity image as the Whisper baseline, ensuring environment consistency. magma framework orchestrates the deployment of the Singularity image plus a custom FastAPI wrapper, allowing the Interactive Playground and other modules to interact with it.

6.2.1.3 Qwen2-Audio

Qwen2-Audio is deployed in a similar fashion to the Whisper baseline, leveraging the native multimodal support within vLLM. This model utilizes the same standardized Singularity image extended with audio dependencies; as the model is supported in vLLM, it is not needed to develop a custom FastAPI wrapper. magma framework is used to properly setup container into MN5 and to expose Qwen2-Audio inference endpoint.

6.2.2 SLAM-ASR: MEUSLI endpoint

MEUSLI²³ is an end-to-end speech-to-text system developed to bridge the gap between pre-trained speech encoders and LLMs, specifically for the European linguistic landscape. Leveraging the **SLAM-ASR**²⁴ framework, it connects a pre-trained speech encoder with a large language model by mapping acoustic features into token-level embeddings for the ASR task.

MEUSLI, as shown in Figure 6.6 is composed by different elements:

- **Speech Encoder:** The system utilizes **Whisper-large-v3-turbo** as its primary acoustic feature extractor. The encoder is kept frozen during the training of the projector to maintain its robust pre-trained acoustic representations.
- **Multilingual Linear Projector:** The core of MEUSLI is a lightweight linear projector that maps high-dimensional acoustic features into the token embedding space of the LLM. Unlike more complex architectures, a linear projector was chosen as it consistently yields superior ASR performance in this framework.

²¹ <https://hub.docker.com/r/vllm/vllm-openai>

²² <https://github.com/m-bain/whisperX>

²³ https://huggingface.co/SpeechTek/MEUSLI_projector_v2

²⁴ <https://github.com/X-LANCE/SLAM-LLM>

- Large Language Model (LLM) Backend: MEUSLI is designed to work with various open-source multilingual backends, including **EuroLLM** (1.7B and 9B) and **Apertus-8B**. The LLM acts as a sophisticated language model that decodes the aligned acoustic embeddings into coherent text.

The model is an open-science effort to provide a unified projector for 28 European languages, covering high-resource (e.g., English, French, Spanish) and lower-resource languages (e.g., Maltese, Welsh, Basque). It was trained on approximately 7,622 hours of diverse audio data from **Common Voice 17.0**, **FLEURS**, and **Vox Populi**. This broad pre-training allows MEUSLI to serve as a powerful initialization point for fine-tuning on low-resource languages or even bootstrapping ASR for languages not seen during initial training. We are exploring how to extend this model to new languages by using Data Reply techniques to introduce new languages and preserve the knowledge of the ones already supported. Further details are available in [deliverable D4.1](#).

Figure 6.6 Proposed MEUSLI (Multilingual EU Speech Linear projector) training pipeline.

6.2.2.1 API Specifications

The MEUSLI model is exposed as a standalone service using FastAPI, designed for interoperability within the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground, to provide transcription services.

The service implements a standardized transcription endpoint:

- **Endpoint:** `POST /v1/audio/transcriptions`
- **Request Format:** `multipart/form-data`
 - `file`: The audio file to be transcribed (typically 16kHz WAV or MP3).
 - `key`: (Optional) A unique identifier for tracking the request
- **Response Format:** `AsrResponse` (JSON)
 - `key`: The provided or generated request ID.
 - `transcription`: The resulting text string.

The FastAPI wrapper manages the model lifecycle and inference pipeline. The Lifespan Management upon startup initializes the `slam_model_asr` via a `model_factory`. This process involves loading the frozen Whisper encoder, the frozen LLM (e.g., EuroLLM-1.7B), and the trained linear projector checkpoint.

Incoming audio files are stored in a temporary directory and loaded using **librosa** to ensure a consistent sample rate. The audio is converted into Mel spectrograms and passed to the encoder which generates speech embeddings, which then are aligned to the LLM space by the projector. These embeddings are concatenated with a fixed text prompt (e.g., "Transcribe Speech to Text") to guide the LLM's generation. Finally, the LLM generates text using a standard decoding strategy (beam search) with a maximum token limit.

6.2.2.2 Containerization Specifics

To ensure the MEUSLI system remains portable and easily integrable within the larger ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground, the deployment strategy centres on a robust containerization architecture using Docker and Docker Compose. This approach abstracts the complex software dependencies required by the SLAM-LLM framework, providing a consistent execution environment across different hardware setups.

The container is built upon a base image optimized for GPU-accelerated workloads, called **pytorch/pytorch:2.1.0-cuda11.8-cudnn8-devel**. Within this environment, the system manages a multi-layered stack of dependencies: it integrates essential low-level audio processing libraries like **ffmpeg**, **sox**, and **libsndfile1-dev**, alongside a highly specific Python ecosystem (including SLAM-ASR). To maintain the structural integrity of the SLAM-LLM framework, critical libraries such as **transformers** (v4.35.2) and **peft** (v0.6.0) are pinned to exact versions, preventing the common issue of "dependency drift" and ensuring that the model behaves identically in development and production.

The deployment architecture is further refined through a modular orchestration strategy. Rather than embedding massive model weights—which can exceed several gigabytes—directly into the Docker image, the system utilizes external volume mounting. This keeps the image lighter. Through the Docker Compose configuration, the container dynamically links to host directories containing the large-scale LLM weights, the Whisper encoder, and the specific MEUSLI projector checkpoints.

This flexibility is managed via environment variables like `LLM_PATH` and `PROJECTOR_CKPT_PATH`, which allow researchers to swap between different language-specific projectors (such as a general 28-language version or a fine-tuned Maltese variant) without rebuilding the container.

6.2.3 Spanish Dialogue-Grounded Spoken Question-Answering System

We develop a dialogue-grounded spoken question-answering system based on the connector paradigm presented throughout deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3. We start out with the standard connector-based speech-LLM paradigm, concretely using Whisper-large-v3 as the speech encoder and both the 2B and 7B instruct variants of the Salamandra LLM developed by BSC as the foundation models for the QA system.

The overall QA task is as follows: given a transcript of a conversation between two Spanish speakers, the system answers questions about the conversation with parts of the conversation acting as potential evidence. The questions are sorted into three categories, following the Pilot 1 conversational testing dataset from D1.2:

1. **Extractive** – Answers to extractive questions are present verbatim in the conversation transcript, usually specific keywords or phrases. The answer to every question can have multiple *required* parts as well as several *permissible variants* of a given single answer (e.g. ["14.00", "at 14.00"]).
2. **Abstractive** – Abstractive questions are aimed at general understanding of the underlying conversation – the answers are not generally present in the text, but they are implied and hinted upon, becoming clear after understanding enough of the context.
3. **Impossible** – Lastly, we have questions that are not possible to answer based on the information presented in the conversation.

In the next section (6.2.3.1), we describe the process of obtaining the QA data for training the QA system. Section 6.2.3.2 then adds some details on the architecture and training process for the QA system.

6.2.3.1 Spanish Dialogue QA Dataset

To support the training of the Spanish dialogue QA model, we created a Spanish speech-question dataset consisting of telephone conversations and spoken questions grounded in the information exchanged in those interactions. In broad terms, the dataset follows the same overall logic as the Pilot 1 test described in [D1.2](#) (Section 3.3.1.1), as it combines conversation audios with questions derived from the information conveyed in those conversations. In the present case, the telephone conversations are synthetic, while the question recordings are based on real speakers. The main difference lies in the role of the dataset within the workflow. Whereas the dataset described in D1.2 is intended for the evaluation of Pilot 1, the present dataset was specifically prepared for model training and development.

Following the same paradigm, we start off with a pre-existing two-speaker conversational ASR dataset as for training purposes, larger amounts of training/finetuning data will be required. For this deliverable, we work with the Spanish speech subset of the **MLC-SLM**²⁵ multilingual conversational ASR challenge dataset. Given that this dataset is not publicly available after the challenge conclusion, we emphasize that the presented data generation pipeline is applicable in the exact same way to other more widely available conversational datasets such as **Fisher Spanish Speech**.

To populate the dataset with high-quality, text-based diverse question-answer pairs, we utilized the **Gemini 2.5 Pro** model. This model was selected for its advanced reasoning capabilities and its ability to maintain context over long conversational windows. For every dialogue segment in the dataset, we generated five pairs for each of the three question categories (extractive, abstractive, impossible), totalling fifteen QA pairs per dialogue. This way, we obtain a dev set of 75 questions and a train set of 4000 questions.

To be able to train the model on spoken queries, we resort to synthesizing the extracted questions using TTS. For this purpose, we utilize two SOTA TTS models with strong voice cloning capabilities: **Chatterbox TTS** and **Qwen-3-TTS-1.7B**. To ensure good voice diversity in the data, we extract short single-speaker utterances from the training MLC-SLM dialogues and use them as the reference voices for the voice cloning. Ultimately, we only utilize the outputs of the Qwen-3 model after some subjective quality assessment and since the Chatterbox TTS has a slight tendency to lean towards South American Spanish accents.

Training speech-LLMs on TTS data can, however, poses some domain overfitting risks as typically, TTS is a problematic data domain that does not generalize well to real-world data. For this purpose, we additionally take the dev set and select a small partition of the training set to be both recorded by native Spanish speakers. This will aid in better generalization of the final system and ensure that evaluations conducted on the dev set will then transfer well to the Pilot 1 test set.

The resulting material is divided into two standard partitions, train and dev (each split contained in its own [train.jsonl](#) and [dev.jsonl](#) file), each paired with its corresponding set of .wav audio files and the dataset is organized around question instances. Each row in the related JSONL files from dev and train partitions represents a single question sample and provides the metadata needed to connect that question to the relevant conversation and speakers. This includes fields such as the sample identifier ([uuid](#)), the [question](#) itself (in natural language), the [question type](#), the conversation identifier ([conversation_id](#)), the [accent](#), the speaker identifiers ([speakers_ids](#)) and the question identifier ([question_id](#)).

²⁵ <https://www.nexdata.ai/competition/mlc-slm>

You can see the format of one question entry below:

```
{
  "uuid": "a3d8766d-a475-492a-8678-b82920a76023",
  "question": "¿Qué aspecto consideran ambos hablantes más crucial que el sueldo en un empleo?",
  "type": "abstractive",
  "conversation_id": "2025_004_phone",
  "accent": "Spanish",
  "speakers_ids": [0, 1],
  "question_id": 3
}
```

A typical entry therefore links a question to a telephone conversation and identifies the speakers associated with its audio recordings. For each question, two audio versions are available, one produced by each of the speakers listed in `speakers_ids`. These audio files are organized according to a consistent naming convention, (`spk{speaker_id}_q{question_id}.wav`) which makes it straightforward to trace each spoken question back to its metadata entry. All audio files are provided in mono, using 44.1 kHz, 16-bit PCM WAV format.

The development split serves as a compact but balanced validation set. It contains 75 questions derived from 5 conversations, with 15 questions per conversation. Its composition is evenly distributed across the three question categories, namely 25 extractive, 25 abstractive and 25 impossible questions. Because each question is recorded twice, once per speaker, the split comprises 150 question audio files, amounting to 17.38 minutes of speech.

The training split is considerably larger and offers broader conversational coverage. It includes 282 questions drawn from 270 conversations, resulting in 564 audio files and a total duration of 60.83 minutes. In terms of question type, the training data has 128 abstractive questions, 114 extractive questions and 40 impossible ones.

6.2.3.2 Architecture and Training of the Spanish QA system

The speech-LLM backbone of the QA system consists of Salamandra LLM (2B and 7B instruct variants) and the Whisper-large-v3 encoder. First, a 2-layer transformer connector module is trained to bridge the representation spaces of the two foundation models using the ASR objective on Spanish Common Voice version 24. The rest of the training/inference paradigm exactly follows the joint spoken FIR/QA system as presented in deliverable 2.3. The dialogue-grounding QA data described in the previous section is used for QA fine-tuning of the ASR-based checkpoint, but since Salamandra only has a context window of 8k tokens, we additionally employ retrieval to only place portions of the conversation that are actually relevant to the question in the LLM context, similarly to how the QA system from D2.3 used retrieval to source Wikipedia documents relevant to the question.

Because the conversations from the MLC-SLM dataset often exceed 8k tokens when tokenized with the Salamandra tokenizer, we chunk them into slightly overlapping segments of 10 speaker turns each, additionally adding the turn number information to each utterance to preserve the continuity of information in the chunks, and annotating the retrieved chunks with chunk number in the LLM context. We keep the chunks overlapping by two dialogue turns as answers to the generated questions (especially the abstractive category) requires cross-turn reasoning and both prior and consequent context is often crucial for answering correctly. The chunk and overlap sizes are hyperparameters that can be tuned at test time. Lastly, compared to regular QA based on an open-ended database of documents, the retrieval in this case serves more of a context compression tool, given that the user only ever asks questions that are related to a given specific conversation – for a conversation of 100 dialogue turns, we only get roughly 10 chunks.

Since Whisper-large-v3 is used as the speech encoder, it is possible to reuse and retrain the speech-query-based FIR branch from D2.3 utilizing the **BGE-M3** model to reduce latency by not having to decode the user's spoken query into text first. However, for best accuracy it is still best to utilize the ASR hypothesis for the user query, as the connector-based retrieval from speech comes with some performance degradation.

The implementation for both training and inference as well as data preparation scripts and checkpoints models can be accessed through the ELOQUENCE WP2 GitHub repository at <https://github.com/pirxus/ELOQUENCE-WP2>.

6.2.4 Wake-up-Word Detection

The Wake-Up-Word (WuW) module is implemented as an Android foreground service that enables hands-free interaction through wake-word detection and automated voice processing. This module is part of the Pilot 1 developed in WP5. Its operation can be understood as a pipeline composed of three main stages.

The first stage consists of persistent monitoring of the audio signal. The process begins with the **AudioService**, a dedicated Android foreground service that ensures continuous access to the device’s microphone. Upon initialization, the service invokes the **Recorder** component, which establishes a low-latency audio stream using the **AudioRecord** class. The resulting raw pulse-code modulation (PCM) data is continuously streamed into a specialized **AudioBuffer**, a thread-safe circular memory structure designed to retain a recent window of acoustic input. At the same time, the *Predictor* class runs on a background thread and performs continuous inference on the contents of the AudioBuffer. To do so, it relies on the **AudioModelsPipe** class, which wraps a TorchScript-optimized GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) model (i.e., [sgru.ptl](#)). This model is specifically trained to identify the “OK, AURA” acoustic pattern in the buffered signal. By analysing the audio in small, overlapping frames, the system achieves accurate wake-word detection while maintaining low computational overhead.

The second stage begins once the wake word has been detected and serves to capture the user’s spoken query. When the WuW is recognized, the **AudioModelsCallback** is triggered, shifting the system from a listening state to a capturing state. At that point, the service executes the `recordUntilSilence` method. This method utilizes Short-Term Energy (RMS) to detect the transition from speech to silence. By calculating the RMS energy over small audio frames, the system maintains a stable and consistent measure of signal strength. The user’s utterance is recorded continuously and the process terminates only after a sustained period of sub-threshold signal is detected. In this way, the system is able to capture the complete spoken request without requiring manual intervention. Once recording has finished, the resulting audio payload is serialized into .wav format. In this context, serialization refers to the conversion of raw PCM audio data into a standard .wav file by appending the appropriate file header, setting the sample rate, bit depth and channels.

The third stage consists of backend processing through the IP developed in Task 5.4 (WP5). The previously generated .wav file is forwarded to the IP via the **EloquenceApiService**. This service is responsible for invoking the different endpoints exposed by the IP and coordinating the communication between the Android App application and the backend services. Currently, in Pilot 1, the WuW module is used to support question-answering interactions.

Throughout the entire lifecycle of the module, synchronization with the application’s user interface is maintained through *Broadcast Intents*. As the service transitions between different states, such as listening, uploading and processing, it emits status updates that are intercepted by the **MainViewModel** in order to provide real-time visual feedback to the user. The MainViewModel acts as the application’s UI state manager and serves as the bridge between the background AudioService, which handles audio acquisition and processing, and the **Compose**

UI, which presents information to the user. Through this mechanism, the AI-generated response is propagated back to the interface so that the user can inspect the result, thereby completing the WuW interaction loop.

6.3 Context and external knowledge

6.3.1 Retrievers and Vector Store

LLMs carry substantial parametric knowledge acquired during pre-training, but this knowledge is inherently static, bounded by a training cutoff, and not specific to the ELOQUENCE project's domain or its evolving documentary corpus. The retrieval infrastructure developed within the Interactive Playground addresses this limitation by dynamically supplying relevant document fragments to the language model at inference time, enabling responses that are grounded in curated, up-to-date, and domain-specific content rather than in potentially stale or irrelevant parametric knowledge. This approach, commonly referred to as Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), has been implemented as a custom-built pipeline rather than adopted from an off-the-shelf framework, enabling precise control over each stage of the retrieval process and direct integration with the platform's task configuration and model interaction systems. The infrastructure is organised around two principal components: a retriever endpoint, which exposes retrieval functionality as an independent HTTP microservice, and a local vector store built on **LanceDB**, which provides the underlying storage and nearest-neighbour search capabilities. The ingestion and query pipelines are illustrated in Figure 6.7 and Figure 6.8 respectively.

6.3.1.1 Retriever endpoint

The retriever endpoint is implemented as an independent FastAPI microservice, decoupled from the main application and operating on a dedicated port. This architectural separation reflects a deliberate design decision to treat retrieval as an independently deployable service rather than an internal library component of the main application. The practical consequences of this separation are significant: the retrieval service can be updated, restarted, or reconfigured independently of the user interface; multiple instances of the main application can share a single retrieval service; and the retrieval functionality can be consumed by components beyond the Interactive Playground itself — as illustrated in Section 6.3.4, where a tool-based integration pattern is described through which a SDialog agent may invoke the retriever's `GET /search` endpoint to retrieve domain-specific document chunks at inference time, without requiring modifications to either framework.

The service exposes four HTTP operations, enumerated as follows:

- `GET /search` — accepts an `index_name`, a query string, and a `top_k` integer parameter; embeds the query using the embedding model associated with the specified index; performs approximate nearest-neighbour search against the corresponding LanceDB table; and returns a ranked list of matching document chunk strings
- `POST /create` — accepts one or more uploaded files via multipart form data alongside ingestion parameters including `chunk_size`, `percentile`, `embed_name`, `table_name`, and `splitting_strategy`; executes the full ingestion pipeline; and registers the new index in the persistent index configuration
- `POST /add` — accepts a text string, a metadata string, and an `index_name`; embeds the provided text and appends it to the specified existing index without requiring a full rebuild
- `GET /list_indices` — returns the names of all currently registered indexes, reflecting the contents of the persistent index configuration file maintained on the filesystem

On the client side, a dedicated **RetrieverClient** class encapsulates all HTTP communication with the retriever endpoint, presenting a clean Python interface — comprising `search()`, `add()`, `create_vs()`, and `list_vs()` methods — that abstracts the underlying request mechanics from the rest of the application. The client accepts either an explicit endpoint URL or the sentinel value "public", which causes it to resolve to the default retriever endpoint as configured in the application settings. This design allows the platform to support multiple named retriever instances selectable at runtime through the user interface, enabling scenarios in which different vector stores are hosted at different network locations and managed independently.

The retriever service is initialised at startup with a persistent connection to the LanceDB storage directory and a **LanceDBRetriever** instance that maintains an in-memory cache of loaded embedding models keyed by model name. This initialisation strategy ensures that embedding models, which carry non-trivial loading overhead, are instantiated once at service startup and reused across all subsequent requests, avoiding per-request model loading latency that would otherwise render the service unsuitable for interactive use.

6.3.1.2 Local Vector Store endpoint

The local vector store (LVS) is built on LanceDB, an embedded columnar vector database that operates directly on the filesystem without requiring a separate database server process. LanceDB persists data in the **Apache Arrow**²⁶ columnar format via **PyArrow**, providing efficient storage and retrieval of high-dimensional floating-point vectors alongside associated text and metadata fields. Each vector index corresponds to a named LanceDB table with a strongly typed schema comprising three fields: a fixed-dimension float32 vector column whose dimensionality is determined by the embedding model specified at index creation time, a string column containing the original document chunk text, and a string column containing source metadata such as the originating file path and page number. Tables are created with an overwrite mode, ensuring that re-ingesting a document collection into an existing index name produces a clean replacement rather than an accumulation of duplicate entries. The embedding model associated with each index is recorded in a persistent JSON configuration file at ingestion time and consulted automatically at query time, guaranteeing that query and document embeddings are always produced by the same model — a correctness requirement that the system enforces without requiring user intervention.

Document ingestion follows a multi-stage pipeline. Uploaded documents are first loaded using format-appropriate document loaders: PDF files are processed with **PyPDFLoader**, Word documents with **Docx2txtLoader**, HTML files with **BSHTMLLoader**, CSV and TSV files with **CSVLoader** configured for the appropriate field delimiter, and plain text and Markdown files with **TextLoader**. Following loading, documents are split into chunks according to one of three user-selectable strategies. The simple strategy divides text at fixed character intervals using a character-level splitter, offering speed at the cost of potentially breaking meaningful textual units. The recursive strategy applies a hierarchical splitting approach using **RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter**, which attempts to preserve natural text boundaries by splitting preferentially at paragraph breaks, then sentence boundaries, then word boundaries, falling back to character-level splitting only when necessary; this strategy produces more semantically coherent chunks and represents the recommended default. The semantic strategy, implemented via **SemanticChunker** from the **langchain-experimental**²⁷ library, takes a fundamentally different approach by using the embedding model itself to identify meaningful breakpoints in the text: consecutive segments are embedded and the cosine similarity between adjacent embeddings is computed, with splits occurring at points where similarity falls below a configurable percentile threshold. This produces chunks that are internally coherent in meaning regardless of syntactic structure, and is particularly effective for heterogeneous documents in which topic transitions do not align with paragraph or sentence breaks.

Following chunking, document segments are embedded in batches of 128 using the embedding model specified at index creation time, with empty segments filtered out prior to embedding to prevent the insertion of vacuous entries into the index. Two sentence-transformer models are currently supported: **sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2**²⁸, which produces 384-dimensional embeddings and offers a favourable balance between computational efficiency and retrieval quality, and **sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2**²⁹, which produces

²⁶ <https://github.com/apache/arrow>

²⁷ <https://github.com/langchain-ai/langchain-experimental>

²⁸ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

²⁹ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2>

768-dimensional embeddings and provides higher representational capacity at greater computational cost. Both models run entirely locally without requiring external API calls, ensuring that the ingestion pipeline remains operational in network-restricted environments and that no document content is transmitted to external services during indexing.

Figure 6.7 Ingestion pipeline of the custom RAG infrastructure.

At query time, the user's input is embedded using the index-appropriate model and submitted to LanceDB's approximate nearest-neighbour search, which returns the top-k most semantically similar document chunks ranked by vector distance. An optional distance threshold may be applied to filter out results whose similarity to the query falls below a configurable minimum, preventing low-relevance documents from entering the model context when no sufficiently similar content exists in the index. Retrieved chunks are rendered into a structured prompt context using a Jinja2 template that formats each chunk as a numbered document accompanied by explicit citation instructions directing the language model to reference specific document numbers when making factual claims, producing responses in which individual statements can be traced back to their source documents. The platform's response post-processing layer normalises citation references across seven distinct patterns that

different language models may produce — including “[doc 1]”, “[document 1]”, “(doc 1)”, “document no. 1”, and their variants — converting all of them into interactive HTML anchor elements that link to the corresponding document displayed in the retrieved context panel. Hovering over a citation in the chat interface highlights the referenced document in the sidebar in a visually distinct manner, providing a direct and transparent provenance verification mechanism that allows users to verify the factual basis of any claim made by the model.

The complete ingestion pipeline — from file upload through format detection, chunking, embedding, and index construction — is accessible both through the platform's graphical Ingestion tab and through the [POST /ingest](#) REST endpoint, ensuring that document collections can be built and updated either interactively by researchers or programmatically as part of automated data preparation workflows.

Figure 6.8 Query and response pipeline of the RAG system.

6.3.2 Name Entity Recognition

As can be noticed from the architecture of ELOQUENCE system (Figure 6.1), the NER instance is called by the Dialog Manager. The entity-based dialog policy of the UNS Dialog Manager is described at 6.1.1 and the experiments of the NER finetuned GLiNER-based model were described in [deliverable D3.2](#). Below, the description of the NER endpoint is documented.

6.3.2.1 NER (GLiNER) endpoint

The specifications of the finetuned GLiNER model are described here. Once a text user/system utterance is given for NER processing, GLiNER returns a json array of objects, each containing the recognized entity, the entity value, the recognition score. If no entity is found in the given text utterance, GLiNER returns an empty list. Thus, according to GLiNER output, the GLiNER endpoint specifications are defined accordingly:

- Endpoint URI path: `POST /v1/chat/NER`
- Content-type: `application/json`
 - Body: `{ "query": "Blah blah blah" }`
 - Description: query - The input utterance (user or system text) to be processed for named entity recognition.

Response:

- Content-type: `application/json`
 - Body: json array of objects
 - Description: each object represents a detected entity with the following fields:
 - `{ "text": "the recognized entity value", "entity": "the recognized entity type", "score": "the recognized entity score" }`

6.3.3 Feedback Loop Integration

Leveraging human feedback is central to aligning large language models with user expectations, since the goal of alignment is to guide models toward producing responses that are more useful, accurate, and preferred by humans. The collected feedback provides the core information needed to support this process:

(1) the user's prompt, such as "What is ELOQUENCE?", (2) the initial LLM response that received feedback, such as "It is a project that...", (3) the user's assessment, which captures free text comments such as "too general," "factually incorrect," or "not what I meant," (4) the feedback query sent by the LLM triggered by the user's feedback, such as "Which part is not clear?", (5) the user's answer to this feedback query, and (6) the revised LLM response generated after incorporating the user's clarification.

This structure makes it possible to form prompt completion pairs in which each prompt is associated with both a less preferred response (the initial completion in (2)), and a more preferred response (the revised completion in (6)), depending on the feedback received. Based on this structure, we propose a feedback loop with two complementary implementations. Based on this structure, we propose a feedback loop with two complementary implementations, Inference time memory pipeline and Post training alignment pipeline.

In the **inference time memory pipeline**, the system uses the information stored in the collected feedback to improve future responses without updating model parameters. The pipeline proceeds as follows. First, each feedback episode is stored as a structured memory entry in a dedicated memory bank or vector store. Second, when a new user prompt is submitted, the system performs similarity matching between the new prompt and previously stored feedback episodes. Third, if relevant past cases are retrieved, the associated corrective signals, especially the user's feedback, clarification, and revised preferred response, are injected into the current prompt as contextual guidance. In this way, the model can reuse earlier corrections during generation time and adapt its behaviour dynamically. The main purpose of this pipeline is therefore to support real time personalization and correction by making past feedback immediately reusable at inference time.

For example: (1) A user submits a prompt: "What is the capital of France?" (2) The LLM generates an initial response: "The capital of France is Paris. It is also the largest city and a major cultural and economic centre." (3)

The user provides a negative assessment: “Too verbose.” (4) The system issues a feedback query: “Which part of the response would you like to change?” (5) The user clarifies: “Only give the city name.” (6) The LLM generates a revised response: “Paris.”

This full interaction is stored as a structured memory entry, including the prompt, the initial response, the user’s feedback and clarification, and the revised preferred response. When a new but similar prompt is submitted, for example: “What is the capital of Italy?” the system performs a similarity search and retrieves the previous feedback entry. The retrieved signal indicates that the user prefers concise answers for this type of factual question. This preference is then injected into the prompt as contextual guidance, for example by adding an instruction such as “provide only the city name.” As a result, the LLM directly generates: “Rome”. In this way, the system leverages past feedback to adapt its behaviour at generation time, enabling consistent and personalized responses without requiring model retraining.

In the **post training alignment** pipeline, the same feedback structure is used to construct training data for subsequent alignment of the model. In particular, the user’s prompt in (1) serves as the shared input, the initial LLM response in (2) is treated as the less preferred or rejected completion, and the revised LLM response in (6) is treated as the more preferred or chosen completion. Based on this process, the system can automatically transform interactive feedback episodes into preference pairs suitable for alignment methods such as Direct Preference Optimization. Unlike the inference time memory pipeline, which improves responses on the fly, the post training alignment pipeline focuses on collecting high quality and human validated supervision signals that can later be used to refine the model more systematically through training.

6.3.4 Integrating Dialogue Agent with a RAG System

Modern conversational agents that are built on LLMs could need to answer questions about specific, up-to-date, or domain-restricted information. For instance, in the context of Pilot 2 we could imagine a University Counsellor Agent that is able to respond to university procedures, course catalogues, and providing institutional contacts. RAG addresses this goal by connecting the LLM to an external knowledge base at inference time. Instead of relying on memorised knowledge, the model first retrieves a small set of relevant text snippets from a vector store, then uses those snippets as context to generate a grounded and accurate response. The result is an agent that can answer domain-specific questions without requiring full model retraining.

The problem examined in this section concerns how to connect SDialog, the dialogue agent framework developed in the context of ELOQUENCE, with an existing RAG backend. For example, with Retriever component of the Interactive Playground (IP).

6.3.4.1 Components and Possible Options

SDialog is a Python library developed at the Idiap Research Institute for building structured multi-agent dialogues. It provides abstractions for personas, agents, and conversations, and it integrates with **LangChain** under the hood to manage LLM calls and tool invocations.

Interactive Playground (IP) is a RAG-enabled chat interface developed internally. It exposes a retrieval service that accepts a query and returns relevant document snippets from a vector store. The underlying store is a LanceDB instance, queryable via a lightweight HTTP endpoint.

Three integration strategies were considered.

The first option was to add a dedicated endpoint to IP and map it from the SDialog side. This would involve modifying IP to expose a new route specifically designed for agent consumption, then writing an adapter within SDialog to call it. While explicit and controllable, this approach introduces tight coupling between the two systems and requires changes to IP’s codebase, which is undesirable if IP is shared infrastructure.

Figure 6.9 - Architecture of the first integration option

The second option was to create a custom **RAGAgent** class within SDialog, effectively reimplementing the LLM invocation logic to intercept queries, call the retrieval service, inject the results into the prompt, and then call the model. This gives maximum control but duplicates logic that LangChain already handles, and it would require maintaining a parallel execution path that diverges from SDialog's standard agent behaviour.

Figure 6.10 - Architecture of the second integration option

The third option was to use SDialog's native tool system, which is built on top of LangChain's tool abstraction. This allows the agent to decide autonomously when to query the knowledge base, without requiring any modifications to either IP or SDialog's core logic. We ultimately decided to adopt this solution.

6.3.4.2 The Tool-Based Solution

In AI applications, tools are functions that allow a LLM to interact with external systems and perform actions beyond simple text generation. So, when tools are used, the LLM can request the execution of specific functions written by developers. These functions may perform tasks such as calling an external API, searching a database, performing calculations, or (as in our case) retrieving updated information. In this way, tools extend the capabilities of the model and allow it to interact with real-world data and services.

Therefore, in the tool-based solution, the SDialog agent is not directly connected to the Retriever component, but it can use these external tool functions to retrieve information when needed. The typical workflow is the following:

1. The agent has a question for the LLM.
 - A. The LLM analyses the request.
 - B. If external knowledge is needed, the model selects and calls a retrieval tool.

2. The tool searches a vector database and returns relevant documents.
3. The LLM uses this information to generate the final response.

SDialog allows plain Python functions to be registered as tools by passing them to the Agent constructor via the `tools` parameter. Inside the engine, these functions will be decorated with LangChain's `@tool` decorator. What the function does require, however, is a well-written *docstring* and a descriptive *name* — both of which the LLM reads directly when deciding whether and how to invoke the tool.

An example of tool function implemented in the context of the ELOQUENCE project is the following:

```
def search_italian_university_data(query: str, docs_k: str = "3") -> dict:
    """
    Search the university counselling knowledge base for guidelines
    and information relevant to the student's situation.

    Use this tool whenever the conversation requires information about:
    - Universities and Department in the italian territory
    - Available resources (offices, contacts, scheduling)

    Args:
        query (str):
            A short, self-contained question or keyword phrase describing
            what information is needed.
        docs_k (str):
            Number of document snippets to retrieve (default: "3").

    Returns:
        dict: A dictionary where each key is "doc1", "doc2", ... "docN" and
            the corresponding value is the text of that retrieved snippet.
            Returns {"error": "<message>"} if the retrieval service fails.
    """
    ...
```

Function's name and docstring are important details because the LLM uses them for understanding the tool's purpose. A vague name like `search_kb` or a missing docstring will lead to unreliable invocation behaviour. Conversely, we need to provide a precise name and a structured docstring describing what the tool does, when to use it, what each parameter expects, and what the return value looks like.

One deliberate design choice worth noting is that `docs_k` is a function parameter, meaning the LLM the opportunity to modulate retrieval depth according to the complexity of the question, requesting more snippets for a broad query and fewer for a narrow one.

```
try:
    top_k = int(docs_k)
except (ValueError, TypeError):
    top_k = 3
```

The remaining part of the function calls IP's `/search` endpoint (with an index-name, a query and the `top_k` value), and then normalises the response into a dictionary of the form `{"doc1": "...", "doc2": "...", ...}`. Finally, it returns the dictionary to the agent. This way, SDialog then injects this result back into the conversation context, and the LLM uses it to formulate its reply.

```
endpoint = "http://localhost:7997/search"
payload = {
    "index_name": "rag_chunks",
    "query": query,
    "top_k": top_k,
}

try:
    response = requests.get(endpoint, params=payload, timeout=10)
    response.raise_for_status()
    results = response.json()
except requests.RequestException as exc:
    return {"error": str(exc)}

if isinstance(results, dict) and "documents" in results:
    items = results["documents"]
else:
    items = results

snippets = [item if isinstance(item, str) else item.get("text", "") for item in items]
return {f"doc{i + 1}": text for i, text in enumerate(snippets)}
```

6.3.4.3 Guidelines for adapting this solution to a different context

The tool instrument works by providing the language model with a description of a function, including its name, the purpose of the function, and the format of the inputs it requires. When the user asks a question, the model analyses the request and decides whether one of the available tools should be used. If it decides that a tool is useful, the model generates a structured request that contains the name of the function and the arguments needed to run it. The application hosting the model then executes the function and returns the result to the model, which uses that information to produce the final response to the user.

The main reasons because we did not produce a reusable solution (for instance with a Factory Method design pattern) is that the function tool's name and docstring cannot be parametrized. To reuse this solution in a different agent or RAG setting, the developer has manually written some code. To this purpose we provide some guidelines.

- The function name should reflect the specific domain of the knowledge base, not a generic label. A name like `search_italian_university_data()` signals clearly to the model when the tool is relevant; a name like `retrieve_documents()` does not.
- The docstring should include an explicit instruction about when to use the tool (the "Use this tool whenever..." section). Without this, the model may either over-invoke the tool on irrelevant turns or under-invoke it when retrieval would genuinely help.
- The developer could also decide to remove `docs_k` parameter or add other personalized ones. It is important that input parameters be simple and well defined, and it is usually better to avoid complex or ambiguous argument structures.
- The return format should be simple and consistent. A flat dictionary of numbered string values is easy for the model to parse and reference. Nested structures or raw JSON arrays tend to increase the risk of the model misreading or ignoring the retrieved content.

It is worth noting that not all language models support tool or function calling. Some older or smaller models cannot produce structured function requests reliably. In general, models designed for advanced conversational agents, such as recent OpenAI models and some other modern LLMs, provide built-in support for tool calling. However, the reliability and accuracy of tool usage may vary depending on the model size and training.

6.4 Dialog-to-Speech

6.4.1 Text-to-Speech endpoint

The text-to-speech endpoint is integrated into Pilot 4, which targets deployment in a child support call centre and requires spoken feedback to be provided to the caller. The primary role of this component is to transform textual dialog output into natural-sounding Serbian speech, target language of the Pilot 4, through a robust, asynchronous API-based architecture. The service is exposed through a lightweight HTTP server and provides a clear request lifecycle consisting of synthesis submission, processing-state monitoring, and audio delivery. In operational terms, a client submits input text and authentication data to the synthesis endpoint, receives a unique request identifier, and can subsequently poll the system for completion status before downloading the generated waveform file.

A client sends a synthesis request to the `/synthesize` endpoint together with user credentials and input text and receives a `request_id` (if the request processing has successfully started). The status of the request is monitored through `/check_status/<request_id>` command and, if it is successfully finished, downloaded from `/get_file/<request_id>`.

From the methodological perspective, the implemented endpoint follows a two-stage neural text-to-speech pipeline. The acoustic modelling stage is based on **Tacotron 2**³⁰, which converts normalized input text into a mel-spectrogram representation. The text is first preprocessed through a symbol and cleaner pipeline, ensuring a consistent sequence representation before inference. Tacotron then generates mel-scale acoustic features that capture the temporal and spectral structure required for speech reconstruction. In the second stage, these mel-spectrograms are passed to a HiFi-GAN vocoder, which synthesizes the corresponding time-domain waveform.

User access is validated through database-backed authentication, with password verification performed using bcrypt-based hashing. In addition, account status and validity periods are checked to ensure that only authorized and active users can submit requests. Each synthesis task is registered in a relational database together with the associated user, input text, output file path, timestamps, and processing state. The request states allow traceability across the full synthesis workflow, covering queued, processed, finished, and failed execution paths.

³⁰ <https://github.com/NVIDIA/tacotron2>

7 User Feedback Implementation

Feedback collection is a crucial process in ensuring that interactions with an LLM improve over time based on user input. It provides a mechanism for capturing user evaluations of the quality, relevance, and helpfulness of model responses. In this deliverable, feedback collection is initiated when specific types of user dissatisfaction or other negative signals are detected in the user's input. Once such a trigger occurs, the system captures a complete feedback episode, consisting of the original prompt, the initial model response, the user's negative signal, the feedback query issued by the system, the user's clarification, and the revised model response.

The **core concept** of the feedback mechanism is:

- **Detection of Negative Signals:** A negative signal is identified when a user expresses dissatisfaction with a response from the LLM. This is usually in the form of phrases like “not helpful,” “incorrect,” or “unsatisfactory.”
- **Triggering Feedback Questions:** Once a negative signal is detected, the system triggers a follow-up feedback question to the user, asking for more specific feedback. The feedback question is generated from a pre-defined set of possible queries, such as “Was this answer helpful?” or “Did you find the response relevant?”
- **Logging the Feedback Episode:** After the user answers the feedback question, the entire interaction cycle, including the initial user query, the LLM's response, the negative signal, the feedback question, and the user's feedback answer, and the revised model response, is logged. This log captures the feedback and helps in the refinement of the model's future responses.

The feedback collection mechanism follows a well-defined sequence:

1. **User Interaction:** The user interacts with the LLM by submitting a query.
2. **Assistant Response:** The LLM generates a response to the user's query.
3. **Negative Signal Detection:** If the user's response indicates dissatisfaction with the assistant's answer (e.g., through keywords or specific phrases), the system detects the negative signal.
4. **Feedback Query Generation:** Upon detecting a negative signal, the system triggers a feedback question to the user, asking for specific information about the quality of the assistant's response.
5. **User Clarification:** The user responds to the feedback question, providing insights into what they found lacking in the response.
6. **Revised Response:** The revised response of the LLM after receiving the user feedback.
7. **Logging the Feedback Episode:** The entire feedback cycle is logged in a structured format.

This feedback process allows the system to collect detailed information from users about areas where the model's performance can be improved, especially when it comes to user satisfaction and the relevance of answers.

7.1 Feedback Implementation with SDialog

In this deliverable, **SDialog** is used to implement the feedback collection mechanism. SDialog provides a set of tools for orchestrating dialogue with large language models, enabling the customization of system behaviour, response management, and feedback collection.

The SDialog is used to:

- Manage the agent's memory, maintaining a coherent conversation flow.
- Control the assistant's response by using orchestrators that define when and how feedback questions are triggered.

- Handle the entire feedback process, including detecting negative signals and triggering feedback questions.

7.1.1 Define the Chat Template

In SDialog, the orchestrator uses **SystemMessage** to insert instructions that alter the behaviour of the LLM. These instructions guide the model to trigger feedback questions or adjust its behaviour in response to specific events during the conversation. However, some LLMs do not support multiple SystemMessage instances within a single conversation.

To address this issue and ensure compatibility with different models, we modify the chat template used by the **llama-server**. The modified template ensures that only a single SystemMessage is injected during the conversation, while still allowing us to “swallow” mid-system messages (such as feedback questions) and convert them to the “user” role when needed. To define the chat template, we will use a **Jinja template** which will be passed to the llama-server using the `--chat-template-file` parameter. The template will take care of turning feedback-related instructions into system messages that can be interpreted correctly by the model.

Here’s the Jinja-based template used in the feedback collection:

```
{% if not add_generation_prompt is defined %}{% set add_generation_prompt = false %}{% endif %}

<|im_start|>system
{% if messages and messages[0]['role'] == 'system' %}
{{ messages[0]['content'] | trim }}
{% endif %}<|im_end|>

{% for message in messages %}
    {% if message['role'] == 'system' %}
        {% if loop.index0 != 0 %}
<|im_start|>user
{{ message['content'] | trim }}<|im_end|>
        {% endif %}
        {% else %}
<|im_start|>{{ message['role'] }}
{{ message['content'] | trim }}<|im_end|>
        {% endif %}
    {% endfor %}

{% if add_generation_prompt %}<|im_start|>assistant
{% endif %}
```

The system message handling ensures that the first SystemMessage is preserved to provide the initial guidance to the model, while subsequent SystemMessage entries are demoted to user role messages to avoid errors in models that don’t support multiple system-level injections. The template first checks if the `add_generation_prompt` variable is defined to handle additional prompts, such as feedback questions. It then checks for any SystemMessage entries, retaining the first one as the model’s guiding instruction and converting subsequent ones to user role messages. Finally, any instructions, like feedback questions, are injected into the conversation flow for proper processing.

7.1.2 Feedback Term definition and Query Bank

Both feedback terms and feedback queries are derived from the Chapter 5 of Deliverable D2.4, *Query-Based Feedback Collection Method*, where feedback is triggered through identifiable negative signals and followed by targeted clarification queries. The feedback terms are used to detect user dissatisfaction signals from natural language input, while the queries provide structured follow-up questions that guide users to articulate more precise and actionable feedback.

The feedback terms are organised into semantically meaningful categories that reflect different dimensions of response failure, including document relevance, factual accuracy, response helpfulness, user satisfaction, and explicit negative signals. Each category contains a set of representative phrases that are used to match user

feedback and trigger the feedback loop. The query bank is aligned with the same categories, and for each category, it provides pairs of feedback queries consisting of a closed-form clarification prompt and an open-ended follow-up question. This design ensures that once a negative signal is detected, the system can issue contextually appropriate queries to elicit more specific user feedback. Some examples of the feedback terms and queries are shown below:

FEEDBACK TERMS	FEEDBACK QUERIES
not what I asked you misunderstood me does not answer my question that is wrong not correct inaccurate this is false not useful still confused too vague not satisfied not good enough I expected more no that is not it this is not what I want	What should I focus on instead? Was I on the topic you meant? Tell me what you want to know Which part is wrong? What should it be? Point to one sentence that is wrong and I will fix it. What would make it useful right now? Do you want a concrete example or a step by step plan? What is missing? What would a better answer look like to you? What should I change to make it work? Tell me what you expected instead. Tell me in one or two sentences what you want; What part should I fix? What should I do differently next?

7.1.3 Instantiate the Agent

The next step is to create and configure an **agent** that will use the SDialog framework to interact with the user. The agent will be responsible for handling dialogue, tracking conversation history, and triggering feedback actions when necessary.

The agent is instantiated as follows:

```
from sdialog.agents import Agent

# Create an agent that will handle the feedback process
agent = Agent(name="FeedbackAgent", model="openai:eurolm.Q4_K_M.gguf", temperature=0.3)
```

Here, we are defining an agent named **FeedbackAgent**. The agent will use a quantized version of **EuroLLM-1.7B** model for processing the conversation. The temperature parameter controls the randomness of the responses generated by the model.

7.1.4 Design the Feedback Orchestrator

The **Feedback Orchestrator** is a key component that dictates when and how feedback questions are triggered. It listens for user dissatisfaction (negative signals) and, when detected, issues a feedback question to the user. After receiving feedback, the orchestrator logs the feedback cycle and resets the state for the next interaction.

In this orchestrator:

- We use **fuzzy matching** to detect negative signals based on the lexicon.
- We also use **embedding-based semantic matching** for cases where fuzzy matching doesn't yield a high enough score.

Once a negative signal is detected, a **feedback question** is generated and returned.

7.1.5 Log the Feedback Cycle

Each triggered feedback interaction is consolidated into a structured feedback record for subsequent analysis and reuse. This record includes the original user query, the initial assistant response, the detected negative signal, the feedback question generated by the system, the user’s clarification, and the revised assistant response.

8 Federated Training implementation

8.1 Core Components

FedEloquence³¹ is a repository that allows the federated training of LLMs and Whisper-based ASR models in both a simulated (standalone) and real network deployment (distributed) mode. It is organized as a layered system where each layer has a clear role. FedEloquence is built on top of the **FederatedScope**³² framework and has been further developed for this project, incorporating additional capabilities and algorithmic improvements tailored to large-model federated training in multilingual settings.

The architecture of FedEloquence is structured into four functional layers, summarized below:

- At the top, the **runner layer** initializes the FL experiment from configurations, decides execution mode and creates the server/client workers.
- In the middle, the **worker layer** (Server, Client) implements FL behaviour through callback functions triggered by incoming message types.
- At the learning layer, **trainers** perform local optimization/evaluation and **aggregators** merge client updates into a new global model.
- At the **transport layer**, communication is abstracted behind a **CommManager**, so FL logic remains the same whether execution is local simulation or real networked deployment.

Figure 8.1 shows a schematic high-level architecture of the framework.

Figure 8.1 Core components of the FedEloquence framework.

³¹ <https://github.com/Telefonica-Scientific-Research/FedEloquence>

³² <https://github.com/alibaba/FederatedScope>

8.2 Communication System

The Communication System in FedEloquence manages message exchange between servers and clients during federated learning. This system enables model updates, configuration instructions and evaluation results to be transmitted between participants in both simulated environments (standalone mode), used in experiments reported in [deliverable D2.3 Section 6](#), and in real-world deployments (distributed mode).

Figure 8.2 The communication flow in federated learning process.

8.2.1 Distributed Mode

In distributed mode, each process is started with a role ([server](#) or [client](#)). The server and clients can run on different machines and communicate over a network using **gRPC**³³ (Google Remote Procedure Call), which makes this suitable for real deployments where data is spread across devices or organizations. gRPC is a client–server communication framework in which participants invoke remote methods through a predefined service interface and efficient binary serialization (Protocol Buffers).

Figure 8.2 shows the communication flow in this distributed FL setting. In the **Initialization Phase**, the server starts its endpoint and waits for `join_in()` messages from clients that want to participate in the federation. Each client starts its local endpoints and then announces itself to the server. Once the expected number of clients has joined, the server starts round-based training by broadcasting current model parameters to the clients selected for that round. Not all clients must participate in every round. The server can sample a subset from client pool with different sampling strategies (uniform, group, responsiveness).

In the **Local Training Phase**, each selected client runs local training on its own private data and then sends model updates back to the server for aggregation. In the **Aggregation Phase**, the server aggregates those updates to build a new global model. This is the shared model that had learned from all the clients that participated in the federation and that will be later redistributed to clients in the next round. This improves privacy because raw data stays local, but it is not a full privacy guarantee by itself (stronger guarantees require mechanisms such as secure aggregation, differential privacy or

³³ <https://github.com/grpc/grpc>, <https://grpc.io>

encryption/secret sharing).

After aggregation, the server can trigger an evaluation round by sending an `evaluate()` message to the selected clients. Each selected client evaluates the current model on its local evaluation splits and reports the resulting metrics to the server. The server then combines these client metrics into global summaries, such as mean, weighted mean and fairness-oriented statistics. Optionally, the server can also evaluate the global model on a server-held dataset. Importantly, evaluation does not need to run after every aggregation. It can be scheduled periodically, such as every `eval.freq` training rounds.

Finally, federated training finishes when the server hits a stop condition, typically reaching the configured maximum number of rounds or an early-stop criterion (for example, global convergence or all clients locally saturated). This monitoring is done in the server. Then, after some final evaluation, the server broadcasts a `finish()` message to all clients through the `comm_manager` (optionally with the final global model parameters). Each client receives that message, updates its local model if parameters are included, finalizes monitoring/logging, and exits its listening loop, so the federated learning process shuts down cleanly.

In Section 8.3, we show the configurations and an example on how to run a FL in distributed mode.

8.2.2 gRPCCommManager

In the repository, `gRPCCommManager` is the transport abstraction used in distributed model to decouple networking from FL logic. Server/client training, sampling and aggregation remain in the worker classes, while `gRPCCommManager` handles only message delivery. **Error! Reference source not found.**, depicts an example of such a communication framework.

At initialization, each participant creates a local gRPC endpoint and keeps a neighbour table that maps `worker_id` to `host:port`. Messages are routed by receiver IDs (targeted unicast) or sent to all neighbours (broadcast

For transmission, the sender creates a gRPC connection (channel) to the destination endpoint and builds a stub, which is the client-side proxy that exposes the remote service methods as if they were local calls. It then serializes the **Message** object into **protobuf** request via `Message.transform()`, calls `sendMessage()` and finally closes the channel.

For reception, each participant runs a small gRPC server endpoint that accepts incoming `sendMessages()` calls in an internal FIFO queue (first-in, first-out). The FL worker loop calls `receive()`, which pops the next queued protobuf payload, parses it back into Message structure via `Message.parse()` and returns it to the application layer. Then the framework routes that message to the appropriate callback according to `msg_type` (e.g., `join_in`, `model_para...`)

The same layer also applies transport-level features such as optional compression and gRPC message-size limits.

Figure 8.3 Real distributed deployment using gRPC as the communication framework.

8.2.3 Message Handling

Message handling in the framework is event-driven and protocol-based. Once a payload is received, it is reconstructed as **Message** object. A Message includes the following fields: `msg_type`, `sender`, `receiver`, `state`, `timestamp` and `content`.

The message is then dispatched to a role-specific callback through the worker's `msg_handlers` registry. `msg_handlers` is the worker's message-routing table: a dictionary that maps each `msg_type` to its corresponding callback function. Both server and clients run continuous receive-dispatch loops, so each `msg_type` triggers a specific workflow action.

In this repository, message handlers are role-specific and refer to incoming message types:

Server-side handlers (messages received by server):

- `join_in`: A client announces itself to the server and shares its endpoint (start federation enrollment).
- `join_in_info`: The client replies with the requested pre-training metadata.
- `model_para (uplink)`: Main training message. Clients returns local model updates after training.
- `metrics`: Client evaluation results.

Client-side handlers (messages received by client):

- `assign_client_id`: The server assigns a runtime ID to a newly joined client.
- `ask_for_join_in_info`: The server requests join metadata (for example sample/resource info).
- `address`: The server broadcasts participants addresses (used in specific modes such as secret sharing).
- `model_para (downlink)`: Main training message. The server sends global model parameters for training.
- `ss_model_para`: Secret-sharing variant of model-parameter exchange for training (optional).
- `evaluate`: The server requests model evaluation on local client split(s).
- `converged`: The server notifies that a convergence/stop condition has been reached.
- `finish`: Final termination signal. It can include final model parameters.

8.3 Server & Client implementation

8.3.1 Configuration Usage

In distributed FL, each participant runs its own process and exchanges messages through gRPC. First, for this mode to be on, both server and client configs must set:

- `federate.mode: distributed`
- `distribute.use: true`
- `distribute.role: server | client`

Then, the IP addresses and ports of the server and clients must be added. The server config file must set its IP address and port under the `server_host` and `server_port` fields. This allows the server to define the central endpoint. Besides, configs in client must set their binding address and port (`client_host` and `client_port`) as well as the IP address and port of the server. It allows them to receive server messages and allow the communications between the entities.

Additional distributed-configuration parameters can be defined to control communication and data assignment. The `data_idx` parameter specifies which data partition a participant uses when a centralized dataset is reused in distributed simulation (setting `data_idx = -1` means the participant uses its full local dataset).

The parameters `grpc_max_send_message_length` and `grpc_max_receive_message_length` define the maximum size (in bytes) of each gRPC message that a participant can send and receive, respectively, which is important when transmitting large model parameters or updates.

Finally, `grpc_compression` configures transport-level compression in the communication layer, with supported options `nocompression`, `deflate` and `gzip`.

Here we can see an example of the configs for running the server and two clients and start the distributed federation between three different linux-based machines:

```
# Server-side (server_2c_200r_30ls.yaml)
federate:
  mode: distributed
  client_num: 2
  process_num: 1
distribute:
  use: True
  server_host: '192.168.24.120' # Server's IP address
  server_port: 11004 # Server's port
  role: 'server'
  data_idx: 0
  grpc_max_send_message_length: 1048576000
  grpc_max_receive_message_length: 1048576000
```

```
# Client-side 1 (client_1_ds_2c_200r_30ls.yaml)
federate:
  mode: distributed
  client_num: 2
  process_num: 1

distribute:
  use: True
  server_host: '192.168.24.120' # Server's IP address
  server_port: 11004 # Server's port
  client_host: '192.168.24.115' # Client's binding address
  client_port: 50060 # Client's binding port
  role: 'client'
  data_idx: 1
  grpc_max_send_message_length: 1048576000
  grpc_max_receive_message_length: 1048576000
```

```
# Client-side 2 (client_2_ds_2c_200r_30ls.yaml)
federate:
  mode: distributed
  client_num: 2
  process_num: 1

distribute:
  use: True
  server_host: '192.168.24.120' # Server's IP address
  server_port: 11004 # Server's port
  client_host: '192.168.24.117' # Client's binding address
  client_port: 50061 # Client's binding port
  role: 'client'
  data_idx: 2
```

```
grpc_max_send_message_length: 1048576000
grpc_max_receive_message_length: 1048576000
```

8.3.2 Examples Usage

To launch real cross-machine FL, start one server process and one process per client machine. Below you can see the commands to run a FL experiment with the server and two clients hosted in different machines. The config files for this experiment can be found in the repository in [configs/distributed/phi-1_5/alpaca_cleaned_en/2c](#). This distributed FL mode in the repository will be used in a demo for Pilot 1 (WP5) to showcase the effectiveness of Federated Learning for adapting LLMs/ASR models while preserving data privacy.

```
# Server in machine 0 (192.168.24.120)
CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0 deepspeed --master_addr=127.0.0.1 --master_port=26100 federatedscope/main.py --cfg
configs/distributed/phi-1_5/alpaca_cleaned_en/2c/server_ds_2c_phi-1_5.yaml

# Client 1 in machine 1 (192.168.24.115)
CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0 deepspeed --master_addr=127.0.0.1 --master_port=26100 federatedscope/main.py --cfg
configs/distributed/phi-1_5/alpaca_cleaned_en/2c/client_1_ds_2c_phi-1_5.yaml

# Client 1 in machine 2 (192.168.24.117)
CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0 deepspeed --master_addr=127.0.0.1 --master_port=26100 federatedscope/main.py --cfg
configs/distributed/phi-1_5/alpaca_cleaned_en/client_2_ds_2c_phi-1_5.yaml
```

8.4 Aggregation Methods

In Federated Learning, aggregation is the process of combining model updates from multiple clients to produce a new global model. Since data remains decentralized on client devices, aggregation plays a central role in enabling collaborative learning without sharing raw data.

In our repository, aggregation is configuration driven. The method is first specified through the parameter `federate.method`. This value is then passed to `get_aggregator()`, where it is mapped via `AGGREGATOR_TYPE` to instantiate the corresponding aggregator class.

During each training round, clients perform local updates on their models and send these updates to the server. The server then applies the selected aggregation rule inside the `_perform_federated_aggregation()` function to compute the updated global model. The different aggregation methods we have been working with are:

- **FedAvg (Federated Average):** It is the most widely used aggregation method in federated learning. It computes the global model as a weighted average of the client models, where the weights are typically proportional to the number of data samples held by each client. Mathematically, the global model is updated as:

$$w^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{n_k}{n} w_k^{(t+1)}$$

where $w^{(t+1)}$ is the updated model from client k after local training, n_k is the number of samples on client k , $n = \sum_k n_k$ is the total number of samples and K is the total number of participating clients.

- **FedProx (Federated Proximal):** It is an extension of FedAvg designed to handle heterogeneous data. The key difference is that FedProx introduces a proximal term in the client's local objective function. This term penalizes large deviations from the global model during local training. Each client minimizes:

$$\mathcal{L}_k(w) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|w - w^{(t)}\|^2$$

where $\mathcal{L}_k(w)$ is the local loss function, $w^{(t)}$ is the current global model and μ is a parameter controlling the strength of the constraint.

- **FedValLoss:** It is a dynamic aggregation strategy where client updates are weighted according to their local validation losses. Instead of averaging all clients equally, the server gives more weight to clients with higher validation loss, so that the global model pays more attention to clients that are farther from convergence.

The formula for the global model update is:

$$\alpha_k^{(t)} = \frac{F_k(w^{(t)})}{\sum_{j=1}^K F_j(w^{(t)})}$$

$$w^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^{(t)} w_k^{(t+1)}$$

where $F_k(w^{(t)})$ is the validation loss of client k evaluated on its local validation dataset, $\alpha_k^{(t)}$ is the aggregation weight assigned to client k at round t , $w_k^{(t+1)}$ is the updated local model from client k after local training,

- **FedInvValLoss:** This aggregation method is the opposite of FedValLoss. It is a dynamic strategy in which the server assigns higher weights to clients with lower validation losses. The idea is to give more influence to clients whose models already generalize well, under the assumption that they provide more reliable updates. For this aggregation, with respect to the previous aggregation method, the only difference is how the weights are computed:

$$\alpha_k^{(t)} = \frac{1}{F_k(w^{(t)})}{\sum_{j=1}^K \frac{1}{F_j(w^{(t)})}}$$

8.5 Training, Evaluation and Monitoring

Federated training is server-orchestrated and message-driven. The logic is the same in simulation and real network execution since the transport layer is kept separate. After enrolment reaches the expected number of participants, the server starts round-based optimization by broadcasting model parameters to a sample client subset.

For each round, every selected client receives the global parameters, updates its local model, executes local training with `trainer.train()` method, and returns a `model_para` message with its training payload. For example, the sample size used in that local training, the resulting trained weights and additional client-side metadata used for aggregation or for termination). The server buffers incoming updates by round (each client update includes a round index: `state`), supports stale-message handling when asynchronous mode is enabled (i.e., can accept with some tolerance updates from older rounds), and moves forward once the minimum number of updates is available. In synchronous mode, it is typically set to `sample_client_num` and in asynchronous to a configured minimum `asyn.min_received_num` or time-based condition (if `time_up` is used).

Evaluation is configurable as server-side, client-side or both using the `make_global_eval` and `make_clients_eval` boolean parameters.

- In server-side evaluation, the server evaluates the current aggregated model on server-held splits.
- In client-side evaluation, the server sends `evaluate()`, clients evaluate the model received from the server and send metrics back.

- The server merges client metrics into global summaries (e.g., average, weighted average, fairness-oriented summaries) and updates tracked best results ([eval_results.log](#)).

Monitoring is implemented through a **Monitor** object attached to each worker (server and clients). During execution, it tracks evaluation history, best-so-far results and system-level runtime indicators, and writes structured logs, such as [eval_results.log](#) and [system_metrics.log](#).

[Eval_results.log](#) records round-wise model performance (server/client roles, round index and metric blocks such as raw/avg/weighted/fairness) in every evaluation round, enabling analysis of learning dynamics over time.

[System_metrics.log](#) records runtime-efficiency summaries (JSON per worker) at termination, including time, communication volume and convergence indicators.

Termination is decided on the server. In the repository, stopping can be triggered by:

1. Maximum configured rounds
2. Global early-stopping criterion (patience/delta over monitored metric, such as the mean validation across clients).
3. Optional local-dynamic criterion (all clients reporting sature in LDES mode). LDES is an early stopping method that enables each client to autonomously decide when to stop and resume local training based on validation performance on its private validation dataset.

8.6 Simulated Experiments

While in Sections 8.2 and 8.3 we focused on the distributed mode of FL, the repository also supports a simulation mode designed for controlled experimentation. As verified in earlier analysis ([D2.1, Section 6.4](#)), this simulation setup introduces no significant differences in model performance. Therefore, it allows us to bypass the communication layer and conduct faster experiments.

Using this simulated mode — configured via the [standalone](#) parameter in [federate.mode](#) — we conducted several experiments with a novel early stopping strategy. We introduce Local Dynamic Early Stopping for Federated Learning (LDES-FL), a method that enables each client to independently decide when to stop and resume local training based on its private validation performance.

In this approach, each client continuously monitors its validation loss and halts local training once no further improvement is observed. The server proceeds with model aggregation. Clients that have already stopped training keep sending their best-performing local model and the server uses this model for aggregation in subsequent rounds. A key feature of our method is adaptive client rejoining. Even after stopping, clients continue to evaluate the validation loss of the global model received from the server. If this global model improves their validation performance, the client resumes local training. The overall federated process terminates only when all clients have stopped.

This dynamic behaviour is illustrated in Figure 8.4, where coloured regions denote active training phases and blank regions indicate idle periods following local early stopping. The experiment shown in the figure corresponds to the federated fine-tuning of the **Salamandra-2B-Instruct** model using 10 clients, each associated with data in a different language. As observed, several clients pause and later resume training multiple times. This indicates that, after stopping, these clients benefit from the aggregated global model and regain improvements in their local validation performance, prompting them to rejoin training. Such behaviour highlights the effectiveness of cross-client knowledge transfer and suggests an interesting direction for future research.

Figure 8.4 Training evolution of 10 clients using LDES-FL with FedAvg..

We compared standard early stopping with LDES-FL across the four aggregation methods introduced in Section 8.4 (FedAvg, FedProx, FedValLoss, and FedInvValLoss), evaluating performance, fairness and computational cost. As shown in Table 1, LDES-FL consistently reduces the number of training steps by nearly an order of magnitude compared to the conventional federated early stopping criterion, which relies on the average validation loss across clients.

This efficiency gain comes at a small cost: LDES-FL slightly degrades both performance and fairness across all aggregation methods. However, increasing the local patience parameter progressively narrows this gap, bringing performance and fairness closer to those of standard federated early stopping, while still maintaining substantial computational savings. Overall, these results highlight the benefits of a client-driven early stopping strategy for achieving more sustainable and efficient federated training. More information about the system and simulated experiments can be found in (Sant, Luque, & Escolano, 2026).

	LDES-FL	Patience	Multilingual Performance	Multilingual Fairness	Total Training Steps
FedAvg	No	1	0.214	6.15E-02	2.20E+05
	Yes	1	0.190	6.81E-02	1.39E+04
	Yes	2	0.198	6.63E-02	2.55E+04
	Yes	3	0.205	6.54E-02	5.71E+04
	Yes	4	0.207	6.36E-02	6.79E+04
	Yes	5	0.207	6.41E-02	8.35E+04
FedProx ($\mu=0.1$)	No	1	0.215	6.18E-02	1.61E+05
	Yes	1	0.197	6.59E-02	1.75E+04
	Yes	2	0.203	6.32E-02	2.54E+04
	Yes	3	0.209	6.33E-02	6.42E+04
	Yes	4	0.210	6.25E-02	6.54E+04
	Yes	5	0.208	6.36E-02	6.98E+04
FedValLoss	No	1	0.213	6.33E-02	1.81E+05
	Yes	1	0.185	6.88E-02	9.25E+03
	Yes	2	0.187	6.90E-02	1.22E+04
	Yes	3	0.198	6.54E-02	2.57E+04
	Yes	4	0.191	6.50E-02	3.01E+04
	Yes	5	0.201	6.54E-02	4.18E+04
FedInvValLoss	No	1	0.213	6.35E-02	2.43E+05
	Yes	1	0.182	6.94E-02	7.30E+03
	Yes	2	0.192	6.85E-02	1.90E+04
	Yes	3	0.196	6.58E-02	2.58E+04
	Yes	4	0.197	6.62E-02	2.64E+04
	Yes	5	0.197	6.61E-02	2.69E+04

Table 1 Comparison of standard early stopping and LDES-FL across four aggregation methods.

We report multilingual performance (mean) and fairness (standard deviation), computed over a test set of 10 languages (501 samples per language), along with total training steps. LDES-FL results are shown for different local patience values.

9 Continuous Alignment and Training Pipeline

9.1 Direct Preference Optimization

Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) optimizes the language model policy directly by maximizing the probability of preferred completions over dispreferred ones, eschewing the explicit reward modelling typically required in standard RLHF. Within the pipeline, the objective is parameterized to minimize the loss function where the model increases the log-probability of the preferred response (y_w) and decreases it for the rejected response (y_l). The hyperparameter β controls the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence penalty, anchoring the trainable policy to a reference model to prevent catastrophic alignment drift. To ensure long-term sustainability and rapid iteration, the optimization strategy strictly employs Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA), ensuring that the foundation model (e.g., [BSC-LT/salamandra-7b-instruct](#)) remains frozen while only the low-rank decomposition matrices are updated.

To ensure long-term sustainability and facilitate rapid iteration within the alignment loop, the optimization strategy employs LoRA for all training procedures. This paradigm mandates that the core parameters of the foundation model, remain entirely frozen and immutable throughout the adaptation process. In place of full-parameter updates, the framework utilizes low-rank decomposition matrices that are injected into specific target modules—typically the attention projection layers—thereby isolating the alignment signal within a lightweight parameter subset. This decoupling ensures that the model's pre-trained knowledge and original capabilities are preserved without the prohibitive computational expenditure or the memory overhead associated with global gradient updates. Furthermore, this modular approach facilitates the storage of multiple independent adapters, allowing for high-granularity version control and the seamless transition between candidate iterations during the deployment lifecycle.

9.1.1 Operational Procedure for Continuous Alignment

The technical execution of the continuous alignment cycle is subdivided into three distinct functional phases: extraction, adaptation, and deployment. This modular workflow ensures the integrity of the `adapter_base` safety anchor while facilitating the iterative integration of user preferences through a high-fidelity feedback loop.

Figure 9.1 Continuous Alignment Loop Diagram

9.1.1.1 Extract, Transform, Load pipeline

The data ingestion process is managed via a programmatic Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipeline hosted on the orchestrator server. This script automates the harvesting of human-in-the-loop evaluations by interrogating the Open WebUI API via a two-stage interrogation procedure:

- **Metadata Harvesting:** A `GET` request is issued to the comprehensive feedback endpoint (`/api/v1/evaluations/feedbacks/all`). This call retrieves a primary index of feedback identifiers along with the corresponding metadata for each evaluation event, enabling the system to identify new entries since the last alignment cycle.
- **Bulk Conversation Retrieval and Collation:** To obtain the necessary dialogue context, the pipeline utilizes the database-level administrative endpoint (`/api/v1/chats/all/db`). This request retrieves the global set of conversations stored within the database.

The collation logic performs an in-memory cross-reference between the metadata harvested in step one and the bulk conversations retrieved in step two. Conversations are selectively retained only if they are tied to a valid feedback identifier, thereby filtering the production data to isolate high-signal preference pairs. By reconstructing these dialogue threads—comprising the user's initial prompt and the model's subsequent response—the system programmatically identifies the "chosen" versus "rejected" trajectories required for Direct Preference Optimization.

The resulting dataset is serialized into the preference-based conversational format supported by the [huggingface/trl](#) library. This schema permits all constituent elements—the prompt, the chosen completion, and the rejected completion—to maintain uneven lengths, thereby obviating the requirement for additional conversation size normalization steps. The data is structured as follows:

```
{
  "id": "unique_identifier",
  "prompt": [{ "role": "user", "content": "..."}],
  "chosen": [{ "role": "assistant", "content": "..."}],
  "rejected": [{ "role": "assistant", "content": "..."}]
}
```

To maintain foundational safeguards, this newly harvested preference data is programmatically integrated with a "retention pack" of safety-validated historical samples from the [adapter_base](#) training set before being promoted to the adaptation phase.

9.1.1.2 Adapter training

The alignment lifecycle starts with the establishment of the [adapter_base](#), engineered to encapsulate foundational helpfulness and safety safeguards. The preliminary dataset for this statistical anchor was synthesized through an exhaustive multi-model evaluation procedure: a vast corpus of prompts was aggregated from diverse sources—primarily mirroring the SFT data mixture—to serve as the interaction backbone. For each prompt, candidate completions were generated using a heterogeneous ensemble of model architectures. These responses were subsequently scored and ranked using an "LLM-as-a-Judge" protocol, utilizing the DeepSeek-V3 architecture to identify high-fidelity pairs for the preference dataset. This synthesis provided the immutable reference policy π_{ref} for all future iterations. This dataset consists of approximately 330,000 preference samples, partitioning in two axes to balance reasoning capabilities with safety constraints: a **helpfulness** subset (comprising roughly 78% of the volume) that utilizes English-centric data to enforce reasoning, structural mathematical formatting, and multi-step logic execution; and a **safeguards** subset (accounting for the remaining 22%) heavily weighted toward Iberian languages—Basque, Spanish, Catalan, and Galician—to establish consistent refusal policies against adversarial vectors involving illegal acts or sensitive socio-cultural queries. To mitigate catastrophic forgetting during continuous deployment, a defined percentage of this baseline data acts as an injected replay buffer across all future training loops, ensuring the initial safety alignment remains robust while establishing the fundamental reference weights required for KL divergence regularization.

Training operations are offloaded to the MN5 HPC cluster, orchestrated through the [rl_salamandra_alignment](#)³⁴ framework. This framework utilizes the CLI to automate the generation and submission of SLURM batch scripts based on declarative YAML configurations. For subsequent adaptation cycles, the nascent [adapter_candidate](#) $\pi_{\theta,i}$ is initialized using parameters from the most recent stable deployment, [adapter_current](#) $\pi_{\theta,i-1}$ while training on a data mixture comprising the original preliminary dataset and the new feedback harvested from Open WebUI. This sequential replay strategy is critical to avoid the catastrophic forgetting of the initial safety alignment.

The DPO loss function is consistently constrained against the [adapter_base](#) to implement a rigorous optimal policy regularization mechanism, mathematically penalizing the model if updated weights induce a distribution that drifts excessively from foundational safety boundaries. High-granularity telemetry is transmitted to Weights & Biases for real-time visualization, with a primary focus on reference log-probabilities as a diagnostic for alignment stability. The training pipeline includes an automated circuit-breaker that terminates the SLURM job if probabilistic deviation exceeds a safe threshold, preventing the generation of unstable weights.

³⁴ https://github.com/langtech-bsc/rl_salamandra_alignment

9.1.1.3 Deployment on vLLM

Upon the successful completion of the DPO training cycle and subsequent empirical validation of the resulting `adapter_candidate`, an automated continuous deployment protocol governs the integration of the updated weights into the production inference environment. A dedicated deployment script migrates the finalized LoRA matrices into a centralized artifact repository accessible to the vLLM orchestrator.

To maximize operational efficiency and maintain high availability for the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground, the architecture heavily leverages vLLM's dynamic multi-LoRA serving capabilities. The deployment script simultaneously updates the symbolic links pointing to the active adapter configuration, ensuring that all incoming inference requests from users are immediately routed through the updated alignment parameters. To mitigate deployment risks, the pipeline enforces a strict version control mechanism, archiving all historical adapter iterations chronologically alongside their respective validation metrics and Weights & Biases telemetry. This highly structured repository functions as a fail-safe continuous integration ledger, enabling instantaneous, automated rollback to a previous, stable LoRA state (such as the established `adapter_base` safety anchor) should anomalous semantic drift or severe out-of-domain hallucinations be detected during live interactions.

10 Conclusion

The successful delivery of the integrated dialogue system described in D2.5 marks a turning point for the ELOQUENCE project, demonstrating that the theoretical and algorithmic advancements made across the consortium can be effectively synthesized into a robust and scalable architecture. The project has successfully moved beyond the baseline definitions established in Milestone 2.1 and 5.1. The deliverable documents on the successful integration of several components developed within all tasks of the WP2, WP3 and WP4, a technical milestone that reaffirms the project's ability to fulfil ELOQUENCE's KR1, 2, 3, 5, and 9 by bridging the gap between technical and ethical alignment.

Using the MareNostrum5 high-performance computing infrastructure, the project has settled a powerful environment that enables both a continuous process for aligning the models through Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) techniques and addresses privacy concerns by integrating a federated training methodology. This demonstrates that the ELOQUENCE models can maintain high performance, adhere to safety guidelines while protect privacy, thereby establishing the necessary foundations to meet the specific helpfulness standards required by our pilot partners in call centres, medical and academic scenarios, and home environments.

Reflecting on the technical journey, the synergy achieved between WP2, WP3, and WP4 stands as the primary achievement of this integration phase. The use of the SDialog's endpoint framework from WP3 has provided the necessary reasoning logic to govern the system, from raw LLMs to complex Dialog Manager's outputs, while the speech-to-text innovations from WP4, including Serbian adapted WhisperX and multilingual MEUSLI integrations, have ensured that the system is truly multimodal and multilingual.

This deliverable has also highlighted the importance of the feedback loop established with WP5; the Interactive Playground and Open WebUI has been setup to provide the empirical data needed to adapt and refine the models trained on MN5.

We anticipate that the assessment methodology developed by WP1 and the ethical feedback integrated by WP6 will ensure the D2.5 architecture and systems will meet the highest European standards for AI safety and societal acceptance.

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